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Combining Geo-Archaeology and Historical Nile Records to Understand Predynastic Settlement Patterns in the Region of the Nile's First Cataract, Egypt

Maria Carmela Gatto | ORCID: 0000-0002-8068-5390

Institute of Mediterranean and Oriental Cultures, Polish Academy of Sciences, Warsaw, Poland; School of Archaeology and Ancient History, University of Leicester, Leicester, UK
mcgatto@iksio.pan.pl

Oren Siegel | ORCID: 0000-0001-9025-1812

Department of Near and Middle Eastern Civilizations, University of Toronto, Toronto, Canada; Institute of Mediterranean and Oriental Cultures, Polish Academy of Sciences, Warsaw, Poland
oren.siegel@utoronto.ca

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Abstract

This paper aims to contribute new data to understanding early Predynastic settlement patterns in Egypt at the beginning of the state formation process in the 4th millennium BCE. It focuses on the early settlements of the First Nile Cataract region. We employ three different datasets to address the issue retrieved from a recent archaeological investigation and drill coring and from Nile records available from archaeological and historical sources. The analysis is performed in a GIS-based environment and through inundation modelling. Data suggest early Predynastic settlements at the First Cataract may have been settled all year round. They appear to be deliberately placed above the annual high flood level and have water resources for most of the year. The new geo-archaeological data further suggests that the average high inundation level for the early 4th millennium BCE was similar to that documented for the end of the millennium.

Keywords

Predynastic settlement pattern – high Nile flood level – Nag el-Qarmila – excavation – drill coring – flood modelling

1 Introduction

The lengthy process that led to the creation of Ancient Egypt, the earliest known territorial polity in human history, started long before the political unification of the country, which was established through radiometric dating and Bayesian modelling at around 3085 BCE (Dee et al. 2013). That event was certainly a threshold in the process but was neither the beginning nor its end. In our opinion, two events can be understood as marking the starting and the end point of the state formation: 1. the development of settled communities in Upper Egypt (archaeologically known as the Naqada culture) and 2. the interruption of the continuously enacted process of making Egypt into a territorial state at the end of the Old Kingdom. Radiocarbon dating (Dee et al. 2013) efforts to place historical chronologies, together with astronomically based models (Gautschy et al. 2017) and a radiocarbon sequence from Upper Nubia (Honegger & Kramer 2017; Schröder 2017), suggest the first event happened around 3800 BCE, the latter around 2300 BCE.

The late settlement of the lower Nile region, particularly Upper Egypt, but also the nearby region of Lower Nubia, has its roots in the type of Neolithization process that took place in Northeastern Africa, with development towards mobile/semi-mobile pastoralism/agro-pastoralism. However, due to the peculiar environmental characteristics of this part of Africa, the economy of the Neolithic communities was always multi-spectrum and opportunistic. Herding, nevertheless, carried a special social and symbolic value within those societies – as can be inferred, for instance, by the use of cattle bucrania in funerary contexts (see the example of Cemetery R12 in Upper Nubia, Salvatori & Usai 2008) – enough to broadly frame them as ‘pastoral’ (Gatto 2021a:126). Indeed, David Wengrow and his colleagues have defined the cultural horizon of the Egyptian and Sudanese Nile Valley in the 5th millennium BCE as a ‘primary pastoral community’ (Wengrow et al. 2014). The climatic deterioration in the Middle Holocene that led to the aridization of the regions on both sides of the Nile (Gatto & Zerboni 2015), with the valley emerging as a sort of long oasis, has contributed to developing more sedentary communities. There is some indication that Nile floods during the height of the *African Humid Period* (c. 8500–5300 BCE) were both higher and more erratic, possibly making

permanent settlement within the lower Nile Valley a difficult or impossible proposition (Zaki et al. 2021: fig. 7). With this aridization, the Nile behavior changed, and floods levels declined (see the special issues by Woodward et al. 2015, for a collection of proxy data). This corresponded with an increase in settlements and funerary remains in the 5th millennium BCE, particularly in Middle Egypt and Upper Nubia, starting the complex transition to more sedentary lifeways attested in the 4th millennium.

The transition from mobile or seasonal occupations to more permanent settlements is, therefore, an important process that needs further investigation. One of the critical problems for archaeologists and Egyptologists is that not much is known about these early settlements. Egyptian settlements, in general, remain understudied, as it was tombs, pyramids, and temples that have always attracted the attention of scholars. This line of research has only recently been enhanced within Egyptology (see, for instance, the seminal monograph by Nadine Moeller (2016), *The Archaeology of Urbanism in Ancient Egypt*, with a critical assessment of the state of the field). Some scholars (see, e.g., Bard 1994:265) assumed that the lack of evidence related to early settlements is because they were mostly close to the riverbanks and are now covered by layers of alluvial silt or modern settlements. The Nile Valley is a pretty restricted space where suitable spots for habitation are limited and tend to be used repeatedly. Where they survive, such dwellings appear to be of limited size, placed at the edge of the valley and built using perishable materials like wood, reed, or mud. They parallel sites from the 5th millennium BCE in the lower and middle Nile Valley that have been interpreted as seasonal occupations (Wengrow et al. 2014:102–103, with references). This, of course, leads one to question their function and degree of occupation. This would not be a significant problem if larger permanent settlements were indeed to be found closer to the river. However, thus far, evidence of early sites with long-lived stratigraphy and architectural features is missing. Wengrow (2006:82–83) suggests that “the arrangement of domestic life remained fluid, just as the materials of construction were for the most part light and ephemeral,” while changing funerary beliefs inspired a kind of ‘urbanization of the dead’ as communities returned to specific cemeteries across generations. Wengrow’s thesis is a compelling narrative we largely agree with. However, we think his argument is essentially an argument from absence that may be challenged by the most recent geo-archaeological evidence. Therefore, the degree to which early 4th millennium BCE settlements in the lower Nile Valley were seasonally or permanently occupied is poorly understood.

This paper aims to contribute new data to the discussion by focusing on settlements from the southernmost part of Upper Egypt, the area of the

First Nile Cataract. The Nile Valley is very narrow and rocky in this area, with desert plateaus reaching the riverbanks in many locations. The river flow is interrupted by granitic outcrops and islands, creating a natural barrage (the cataract) and making navigation challenging. The region is, thus, a natural boundary, which became the southern border of the Ancient Egypt state from the end of the 4th millennium BCE. The regional center was built at Elephantine Island (modern-day Aswan), at the northern tip of the cataract. The sites identified so far, small in size and with ephemeral architecture, are found close to the river, in the only space available. According to current understanding, their formal characteristics and the potential impact of the summer river flooding would suggest a seasonal use of those sites. But was that the case? We will use three different datasets to address this question. Recent archaeological excavations and drill coring in the area north of the cataract respectively contribute two datasets that directly inform our knowledge of the region. The sites' small size and marginal geographical location provide a much-needed bottom-up perspective to the study of early Predynastic settlement patterns. The third dataset is comprised of Nile records derived from archaeological sources complemented by later historical records. The combined analysis of those datasets was achieved using QGIS to perform spatial analyses and model inundation patterns. We argue that archaeological and geophysical evidence from the First Cataract region suggests that even these smaller villages were likely occupied continuously throughout the year rather than seasonally because they were intentionally placed out of reach of the Nile flood, though the limited evidence makes this a hypothesis rather than a definitive conclusion and because they have available water resources, and possible farming land for the most part of the year.

2 Archaeological Data

We concentrate our efforts on a stretch of the Nile Valley comprised between the modern cities of Aswan and Kom Ombo (Fig. 1), which has been the focus of recent geo-archaeological investigations by several projects, the most prominent for our purposes being the Aswan-Kom Ombo Archaeological Project (AKAP). The ongoing work by AKAP has concentrated on the west bank of the Nile north of Aswan, more precisely from the elite necropolis of Qubbet el-Hawa to one of the largest side valleys south of the Kom Ombo Plain called Wadi el-Tawil and in the two major wadis intersecting the valley north of the cataract from both sides (Wadi Kubbaniya and Wadi Abu Subeira). The

FIGURE 1 Map of the area north of Aswan with sites mentioned in the text.

wealth of data provided on a regional scale and along the Nile by the project is significant, considering most of the archaeological research in Egypt still deals with single sites or a single monument within a site.

A total of 53 sites were recorded in the area under examination (Table 1). In relative chronology, they date to the Naqada IA¹–IIB (Phase 1) and Naqada IICD (Phase 2), which correspond in absolute chronology to c. 3800–3300 BCE. The vast majority consists of rock art locales (40 entries); 5 are isolated or small clusters of artifacts, the function of which is somehow difficult to determine; 4 sites have a funerary function; and 4 are domestic settlements.

The domestic and funerary sites found by AKAP deserve further attention. They were found in 5 different locales on the west bank, near the mouths

1 A re-examination of the pottery sequence from Upper Egyptian sites, such as Abydos (Hartmann 2016) and Adāima (Buchež 2021), has recently suggested that some of the pottery traditionally attributed to the Naqada IC phase could, in fact, date to the Naqada IA phase. This revolutionizes the current understanding of the geographical origin and expansion of the Naqada culture throughout the Nile Valley (Gatto 2021b:129) and supports an earlier date also for our sites, so far attributed to Naqada IC (Gatto et al. 2009b). This change, however, concerns only the relative chronology because the whole Naqada IA-C phase, according to available radiometric determinations, falls within the same temporal bracket.

TABLE 1 Archaeological Site List.

Name	Locality	Macrotype	Site Type	Phase 1	Phase 2	C14	Accuracy	Bibliography	Project	xcoord	ycoord
WT2	Wadi el-Tawil	Isolated/ Scatter of Finds	Scatter of Artifacts	X	X	\	2	Unpublished	AKAP	3660181.716	2786675.431
WT4	Wadi el-Tawil	Isolated/ Scatter of Finds	Scatter of Artifacts	X	X	\	2	Unpublished	AKAP	3660095.441	2786625.345
WT5	Wadi el-Tawil	Isolated/ Scatter of Finds	Scatter of Artifacts	X	X	\	3	Unpublished	AKAP	3659982.821	2786475.929
WT6	Wadi el-Tawil	Settlement	Storage Area	X	X	\	5	Oliveira 2023	AKAP	3660689.204	2787184.542
WT7	Wadi el-Tawil	Rock Art	Isolated Rock Art	X	X	\	2	Unpublished	AKAP	3660625.647	2787460.238
WT11	Wadi el-Tawil	Rock Art	Isolated Rock Art	X	X	\	2	Unpublished	AKAP	3659814.17	2787208.237
WT12a	Wadi el-Tawil	Rock Art	Cluster of Rock Art	X	X	\	4	Gatto 2021	AKAP	3659647.47	2787495.6
WT16	Wadi el-Tawil	Rock Art	Cluster of Rock Art	X	X	\	2	Unpublished	AKAP	3659842.882	2786757.757
WT26	Wadi el-Tawil	Rock Art	Isolated Rock Art	X	X	\	3	Unpublished	AKAP	3659753.936	2787615.916

TABLE 1 Archaeological Site List. (*cont.*)

Name	Locality	Macrotype	Site Type	Phase 1	Phase 2	C14	Accuracy	Bibliography	Project	xcoord	ycoord
WT 27	Wadi el-Tawil	Settlement	Village	X	X	\	4	Unpublished	AKAP	3660537.558	2787067.323
AH3	Abu Heta	Rock Art	Isolated Rock Art	X	\	\	3	Unpublished	AKAP	3657679.13	2784612.682
Khor el-Aqaba el-Saghira North	Khor el-Aqaba el-Saghira	Rock Art	Cluster of Rock Art	X	X	\	1	Kelany 2020	SCA	3661851.643	2783390.588
Khor el-Aqaba el-Saghira South	Khor el-Aqaba el-Saghira	Rock Art	Cluster of Rock Art	X	X	\	1	Kelany 2020	SCA	3662440.388	2782636.815
KASN1	Khor Abu Subeira North	Rock Art	Cluster of Rock Art	X	X	\	2	Unpublished	AKAP	3665573.676	2780103.425
KASN2	Khor Abu Subeira North	Rock Art	Isolated Rock Art	X	X	\	2	Unpublished	AKAP	3665520.153	2780286.293
Wadi el Malik	Wadi el Malik	Rock Art	Dispersed Concentration of Rock Art	X	X	\	2	Morenz <i>et al.</i> 2020	SCA; Bonn	3668824.147	2777614.043
WAS1	Wadi Abu Subeira	Rock Art	Cluster of Rock Art	X	X	\	3	Gatto <i>et al.</i> 2009c, 19	AKAP	3659837.617	2780408.424

TABLE 1 Archaeological Site List. (*cont.*)

Name	Locality	Macrotype	Site Type	Phase 1	Phase 2	C14	Accuracy	Bibliography	Project	xcoord	ycoord
WAS6	Wadi Abu Subeira	Rock Art	Clustered Concentration of Rock Art	X	X		4	Červíček 1974, 92–96; Storemyr <i>et al.</i> 2008, 155–158; Gatto <i>et al.</i> 2009c, 19; Kelany 2013 and 2020	AKAP	3662057.197	2779685.771
WAS8	Wadi Abu Subeira	Rock Art	Isolated Rock Art	X	X		2	Unpublished	AKAP	3664440.786	2779456.696
WAS17	Wadi Abu Subeira	Rock Art	Isolated Rock Art	X	X		2	Unpublished	AKAP	3661556.155	2780605.197
WAS19	Wadi Abu Subeira	Rock Art	Cluster of Rock Art	X	X		2	Unpublished	AKAP	3661200.454	2780309.709

TABLE 1 Archaeological Site List. (cont.)

Name	Locality	Macrotype	Site Type	Phase 1	Phase 2	C14	Accuracy	Bibliography	Project	xcoord	ycoord
KASS1	Khor Abu Subeira South	Rock Art	Dispersed Concentration of Rock Art	X	X		4	Murray and Myers 1933; Gatto <i>et al.</i> 2009a; Curci <i>et al.</i> 2012; Lippiello 2012; Lippiello and Gatto 2012	AKAP	3665738.807	2776238.073
KASS7	Khor Abu Subeira South	Rock Art	Isolated Rock Art	X	X		2	Unpublished	AKAP	3666063.287	2775614.761
KASS10	Khor Abu Subeira South	Rock Art	Cluster of Rock Art		X		2	Unpublished	AKAP	3665845.852	2776947.348
Wadi el-Arab	Wadi el-Arab	Rock Art	Cluster of Rock Art	X	X		2	Kelany 2018	SCA	3660983.02	2774152.13
Wadi Sheikh Umran	Wadi Sheikh Umran	Rock Art	Cluster of Rock Art		X		2	Kelany 2018	SCA	3661210.49	2773871.138
Wadi Agbab	Wadi Agbab	Rock Art	Cluster of Rock Art		X		2	Kelany 2018	SCA	3661660.969	2773233.33

TABLE 1 Archaeological Site List. (cont.)

Name	Locality	Macrotype	Site Type	Phase 1	Phase 2	C14	Accuracy	Bibliography	Project	xcoord	ycoord
WK6	Wadi Kubbaniya	Cemetery	Small-size Cemetery	X	X		3	Junker 1920	AKAP; ÖAW	3657634.528	2779099.881
WK14	Wadi Kubbaniya	Cemetery	Medium-size Cemetery	X	X		5	Gatto 2009, 2013, 2014 and 2016; Gatto <i>et al.</i> 2009b, 2009c and 2010; Pitre <i>et al.</i> 2016; Hart 2017	AKAP	3658082.778	2782213.097
WK15	Wadi Kubbaniya	Settlement	Village	X	X	4230 ± 50BP (IFAO152); 4955 ± 50BP (IFAO153); 4917 ± 50BP (IFAO151); 5040 ± 50BP (IFAO154)	5	Gatto 2009, 2013, 2014 and 2016; Gatto <i>et al.</i> 2009b, 2009c and 2010; Pitre <i>et al.</i> 2016; Hart 2017	AKAP	3658051.556	2782150.654
WK16	Wadi Kubbaniya	Rock Art	Cluster of Rock Art		X		3	Unpublished	AKAP	3658098.388	2777726.141
WK19	Wadi Kubbaniya	Rock Art	Cluster of Rock Art	X			2	Unpublished	AKAP	3655631.9	2782143.964

TABLE 1 Archaeological Site List. (cont.)

Name	Locality	Macrotype	Site Type	Phase 1	Phase 2	C14	Accuracy	Bibliography	Project	xcoord	ycoord
WK22	Wadi Kubbaniya	Settlement	Storage Area	X	X		5	Gatto 2009, 2013, 2014 and 2016; Gatto <i>et al.</i> 2009b, 2009c and 2010; Pitre <i>et al.</i> 2016; Hart 2017; Oliveira 2023	AKAP	3657935.591	2782007.928
WK39	Wadi Kubbaniya	Rock Art	Cluster of Rock Art	X	X		3	Unpublished	AKAP	3655422.271	2778751.985
WK41	Wadi Kubbaniya	Rock Art	Isolated Rock Art		X		2	Unpublished	AKAP	3655208.182	2779153.403
WK50	Wadi Kubbaniya	Isolated/ Scatter of Finds	Scatter of Artifacts	X	X		2	Unpublished	AKAP	3651132.679	2787909.324
WK58	Wadi Kubbaniya	Isolated/ Scatter of Finds	Isolated Find		X		3	Unpublished	AKAP	3651054.068	2787824.023
WK70	Wadi Kubbaniya	Rock Art	Isolated Rock Art		X		3	Unpublished	AKAP	3657987.25	2782377.716

TABLE 1 Archaeological Site List. (*cont.*)

Name	Locality	Macrotype	Site Type	Phase 1	Phase 2	C14	Accuracy	Bibliography	Project	xcoord	ycoord
SM6	Sheikh Mohamed	Cemetery	Large-size Cemetery	X	X	\	5	Junker 1919	AKAP; ÖAW	3658561.691	2774295.693
SM13	Sheikh Mohamed	Rock Art	Clustered Concentration of Rock Art	X	X	\	4	de Morgan <i>et al.</i> 1894; Gatto <i>et al.</i> 2009a and 2009c	AKAP	3658285.717	2776530.808
SM16	Sheikh Mohamed	Rock Art	Dispersed Concentration of Rock Art	X	X	\	4	Gatto <i>et al.</i> 2009a and 2009c	AKAP	3658882.268	2773273.472
SM18	Sheikh Mohamed	Rock Art	Cluster of Rock Art	X	X	\	4	Unpublished	AKAP	3658383.283	2775376.175
SM26	Sheikh Mohamed	Rock Art	Cluster of Rock Art	X	X	\	4	Unpublished	AKAP	3658281.827	2774300.323
WQ17	Wadi el-Qurna	Rock Art	Isolated Rock Art	\	X	\	2	Unpublished	AKAP	3657289.492	2771026.888
WQ22	Wadi el-Qurna	Rock Art	Cluster of Rock Art	\	X	\	2	Unpublished	AKAP	3657539.749	2774086.064
WF15	Wadi el-Faras	Rock Art	Cluster of Rock Art	X	X	\	3	Unpublished	AKAP	3658460.779	2769782.254

TABLE 1 Archaeological Site List. (*cont.*)

Name	Locality	Macrotype	Site Type	Phase 1	Phase 2	C14	Accuracy	Bibliography	Project	xcoord	ycoord
WF16	Wadi el-Faras	Rock Art	Clustered Concentration of Rock Art	X	X	\	4	Winkler 1939; Storemyr 2009	AKAP; Quarryscapes	3657652.369	2769543.634
WF17	Wadi el-Faras	Rock Art	Cluster of Rock Art	X	X	\	4	Storemyr 2009 (Gazelle Hill/EB129A-D, P825)	AKAP; Quarryscapes	3658240.557	2768581.347
WF18	Wadi el-Faras	Rock Art	Cluster of Rock Art	X	X	\	4	Storemyr 2009 (Giraffe Hill, EB128A-D)	AKAP; Quarryscapes	3658353.212	2768324.99
WF19	Wadi el-Faras	Rock Art	Isolated Rock Art	X	\	\	3	Unpublished	AKAP	3657926.671	2769568.165
NH12 Panel 2 (giraffe)	Nag el-Hamdulab	Rock Art	Isolated Rock Art	X	X	\	4	Unpublished	AKAP	3659547.434	2770795.628
NH16	Nag el-Hamdulab	Cemetery	Funerary Monument	X	X	\	4	Unpublished	AKAP	3659010.498	2769414.288

TABLE 1 Archaeological Site List. (*cont.*)

Name	Locality	Macrotype	Site Type	Phase 1	Phase 2	C14	Accuracy	Bibliography	Project	xcoord	ycoord
Wadi Abu Agag Loc. 4	Wadi Abu Agag	Rock Art	Cluster of Rock Art		X		3	Schweinfurth 1912		3666397.732	2768275.091

The archaeological projects cited in abbreviations are:

AKAP: Aswan-Kom Ombo Archaeological Project

Bonn: Bonner Rheinischen Friedtech-Wilhelms-Universität

DAIK: Deutsches Archäologisches Institut Kairo

öAW: Österreichische Akademie der Wissenschaften

Quarryscapes: QuarryScapes Project

SCA: Supreme Council of Antiquities

of wadis extending into the Western Desert. From north to south, they are distributed as follows (Fig. 1):

1. Wadi el-Tawil – this is the largest wadi with a catchment area before the opening of the Nile Valley into the Kom Ombo Plain from the south, c. 20 km north of Aswan. A large concentration of ceramic fragments, lithic artefacts, and some animal bones was identified on the terrace at the northern edge of the wadi's mouth. No architectural features were visible from the surface. The archaeological evidence (labelled WT27, Gatto 2021b) is consistent with that found in the next valley south (Nag el-Qarmila, see below), which has been interpreted as a village through excavation. Unfortunately, the area is heavily damaged by modern construction, and further investigation cannot be pursued. On top of the nearby lowest terrace of the northern plateau, several storage pits were identified in an area disturbed by modern quarrying (WT6, Oliveira 2023). The pottery found at the site parallels in type and chronology that found below in the settlement. The use of the pits also to store cereals is supported by botanical remains currently under investigation.² No cemetery was found in the valley, but one may have existed near the settlement (as suggested by the evidence in Nag el-Qarmila).³
2. Nag el-Qarmila – the next valley is located c. 17 km north of Aswan. A village (WK15) with an adjoining burial ground (WK14) was identified on the northern side of the wadi's mouth. The storage facility (WK22) was on the lower terrace of the plateau on the wadi's southern side, overlooking the domestic quarters. All three sites were partially excavated by AKAP (Gatto 2009; Gatto 2013; Gatto 2014; Gatto 2016; Gatto 2021b; Gatto et al. 2009a; Gatto et al. 2009b; Gatto et al. 2009c; Gatto et al. 2010) and provide the most detailed information at our disposal (see next section).
3. Wadi Kubbaniya – this is the largest wadi intersecting the valley from the west, north of the cataract, c. 15 km north of Aswan. At the mouth's southern side, on ancient Late Pleistocene Nile alluvium, a small burial ground (Kubbaniya North, in Junker 1920) was excavated over a hundred years ago. No settlement was reported nearby, but no efforts were made to find any. Nonetheless, a survey by AKAP in the area failed to find domestic installations. Some drill cores made closer to the wadi bottom, where the modern village is located, have revealed pottery sherds dated to dynastic times, though none from earlier periods.

² Ahmed & El Dory (2022).

³ WT6 was partially used as a cemetery during the Naqada III phase.

4. Sheikh Mohamed – this is the next large valley to the south, located c. 10 km north of Aswan. Here, the largest cemetery north of the cataract was excavated a hundred years ago by Ermann Junker (Kubbaniya South, Junker 1919). Junker's team found no settlement in the valley, a fact which could not be changed by a recent extensive survey by AKAP. Possibly, the associated settlement was located on the island in front of Sheikh Mohamed, now incorporated into the east bank, where drill cores by the German Archaeological Institute have identified remains dated to the Greco-Roman period, mainly pottery, but no earlier material (Klose 2017).
5. Nag el-Hamdulab – this valley, only 6 km north of Aswan, is famous for being the place of one of the most important rock art cycles of Dynasty Zero (Hendrickx et al. 2012). On top of the plateau overlooking the valley, AKAP recently investigated a funerary monument (NH16, Bourgeois et al. 2024) composed of a large stone ring enclosing two possible grave shafts and a few offering pits. Adjacent to the ring, on its western side, a smaller ring was added later to enclose another tomb. The funerary complex was already plundered, but the pottery identified suggests a quite extended use, from Naqada II to Naqada III (c. 3500–3100 BCE). The original structure, the oldest, was probably that of an important individual of the pastoral mobile community roaming the desert hinterland of the cataract. Therefore, it is not pertinent to our current research question.

2.1 *The Predynastic Sites of Nag el-Qarmila*

The sites in Nag el-Qarmila are the only set of domestic, storage and funerary quarters (Fig. 2) associated with a single community ever studied in the southernmost part of Ancient Egypt (Gatto 2016). Although damaged by modern human activities and only partially investigated, the sites provide significant information for our purpose. Four areas were excavated in the village (including Area A and Area B), and four radiocarbon dates were obtained from samples collected in Area B (Gatto et al. 2009b). The latter has yielded the most interesting deposit, unfortunately, disturbed on its western side by the presence of quarrying pits, which may be as early as the late Naqada period (Naqada III) in date.

The stratigraphic sequence at Area B was covered by a very thin and deflated layer (1) of cobbles, aeolian sand, and archaeological material. Below it was a layer of aeolian sand (2), absent to the south and deeper to the north, with almost no associated archaeological material. This corresponds to a dune recorded during a geomagnetic survey (Gatto et al. 2009b) and confirmed by drill coring (see below), which seems to cover the eastern part of the settlement, the

FIGURE 2 Map of Nag el-Qarmila valley with information about archaeological sites, drill cores, and landscape geomorphology.

cemetery, and the northern section of the inner valley. Layer 3 was right below the sand, while to the south, it lay directly below the surface. The matrix was a loose, light-yellow sand containing variable amounts of greyish-brown silt in thin laminate layers and loose patches, with the percentage of silt increasing toward the south. Two small hearths (H₁ and H₃) were associated with it, both in the excavation's central-southern section. At its top, the remains of an acacia bush were recorded and radiocarbon dated to 4230 ± 50 BP, 2821–2630 cal. BCE (IFAO 152).

The first well-preserved occupation surface, Layer 11, was next in stratigraphic position (Fig. 3). Two working/living surfaces were associated. Feature 2 (F₂), located in the northwestern corner of the area and only partially exposed, consisted of burnt, clean aeolian sand with artifacts found on its top. The identified evidence of burning may be associated with a fire event, which would have destroyed a possible ephemeral superstructure. Hearth 4 (H₄), located south of the excavation, was comprised of more concentrations of ash-dark sediment, which led to an initial definition of the feature as a hearth (hence its label), but it can be more properly defined as a working area. In association were lithics, potsherds, animal bones (including fish), a bone awl, and a spot of charcoal, the latter radiocarbon dated to 4955 ± 50 BP, 3806–3644 cal. BCE (IFAO 153). A deep bowl of coarse shale ware was found in situ set into

FIGURE 3 Nag el-Qarmila village WK15, plan of Layer 11 (later occupation).

the ground to the eastern side of the excavated area. All the above-mentioned features may have been located within an open-air space or a courtyard, a fact suggested by the finding of a few sheep/goat coprolites in the area between F2 and H4.

The following occupation phase, Layer 16, comprised the bottom part of the stratigraphy (Fig. 4). A concentration of four hearths (H6–9) was recorded in stratigraphical sequence in the northwestern corner, right below F2 (Fig. 5). Two mud-lined pits (F3 and F4) were found set into the ground to the east of the hearths, with one possibly reused as posthole. Other postholes, including one of the so-called *calàge en pot* type (Midant-Reynes & Buchez 2002:41–43; Anderson 2006:115–117; Tristant 2004:106), were found in the

FIGURE 4 Nag el-Qarmila village WK15, plan of Layer 16 (earlier occupation).

southern half of Area B, all in association with a floor area. The lowermost hearth in the sequence, H6, was radiocarbon dated to 4917 ± 50 BP, 3799–3635 cal. BCE (IFA0 151). The hearth was capped by a thin layer of rubified sand and a concentration of broken rocks and artifacts. Adjacent to H6, and set into the ground, was found a pot. Two other isolated potential postholes were found below Layer 16's floor; however, their anthropic nature could not be confirmed. On the sterile soil level below that floor, the root of an *Acacia* tree was found, and radiocarbon dated to 5040 ± 50 BP, 3956–3712 cal. BCE (IFA0 154).

Significantly, no phases of abandonment or layers of alluvial or aeolian deposit have been found intermingled with the occupational phases. This is true despite the nature of most of the deposits being aeolian sand or Late

FIGURE 5 Nag el-Qarmila village WK15, sequence of hearths associated with the earlier occupation.

Pleistocene alluvium. Lenses of one in contexts where the other is dominant are the results of post-depositional bioturbation and anthropic disturbance.

Area A was on the outer edge of the settlement, to the south (Fig. 2). There were two main levels of activity evident in this settlement sector. Here, the deposit was looser than in Area B due to a thick layer of aeolian sand. The features in the uppermost level consisted of multiple hearths, a large in situ stone mortar, and a small pit filled with stones. That assemblage and the lack of clear structural features or midden deposits indicate that this area was likely used for production activities. The charcoal associated with the hearths

has not been dated yet, and the chronological attribution of this phase to the Predynastic period cannot be confirmed at this stage, although all the material culture found around the features is from that period. The lower layer of activity consisted of a few artifact concentrations and a child burial on the south side of the unit. The burial was underneath a burnt surface but not directly associated with it because the two features were separated by sand layers, possibly placed intentionally to cover the child. This child was about 1 year old (\pm 4 months) and has the earliest identified case of scurvy in Egypt (Pitre et al. 2016). Lenses of dark sediments are visible, particularly closer to the hearths of the top occupation, but, again, no clear intermixing with potential alluvial sediments was identified. The child skeleton was found in a relatively good state of preservation, which may suggest the area was usually beyond the average annual high flood level.

Topographical elevations around WK15 (Table 2) were retrieved employing Imaging Station in 2011 and documented how most of the settlement was built at an elevation of c. 92.50 and 93.50 m a.s.l.; Area B is located at an elevation of 93.00/93.50 m a.s.l., and Area A is lower at an elevation of 92.50 m a.s.l. (Fig. 6).

For our purposes, the key element to take away from the archaeological record is that the early stratigraphical deposits in Area B, dated to Phase 1, that is, to the first half of the millennium, do not show any intermingle of occupational and alluvial/aeolian sediments. This fact suggests that no significant episodes of flooding or abandonments are detected in the stratigraphical sequence. Of course, this is not decisive evidence in favour or against a potential seasonal or long-term site use. It mainly argues for the intentionality of keeping the domestic quarters out of the Nile annual flooding. Important to keep in mind is also the topographical elevation of the site, higher than 92.50 m a.s.l.

3 Data from Drill Cores

Between 2007 and 2012, a total of 31 drill cores were performed by the German Archaeological Institute in Cairo and AKAP⁴ in Nag el-Qarmila, only partially published by Gatto et al. (2009b) (Fig. 7). The aim was to retrieve information about the geology of the surface materials and the valley's geomorphology and understand the geoarchaeological context of the Predynastic sites. The drillings were done using Eijkelkamp hand auger equipment. Edelman-, riverside- and stony soil augers were used according to the sediment type. Hand-operated

4 Under the supervision of Dietrich Raue, in collaboration with the late Morgan De Dapper, University of Ghent.

TABLE 2 Elevation points from the area of the Predynastic village of Nag el-Qarmila (WK15).

Name	Elev	Range	Range2	Year	xcoord	ycoord
4703	93.423	> 93.3m	93–93.5m	2011	32.86057134	24.23585801
4806	93.481	> 93.3m	93–93.5m	2011	32.8606014	24.23585359
48B5	93.789	> 93.3m	93.5–94m	2011	32.8607798	24.23582596
48E6	93.920	> 93.3m	93.5–94m	2011	32.86094931	24.23582625
4956	93.739	> 93.3m	93.5–94m	2011	32.86102463	24.2358076
49B8	92.767	92–93m	92.5–93m	2011	32.86118749	24.23576912
49B1	92.569	92–93m	92.5–93m	2011	32.86116126	24.23573751
49AA	92.573	92–93m	92.5–93m	2011	32.86110647	24.23567666
49A3	92.447	92–93m	92–92.5m	2011	32.86106253	24.23561769
495D	93.140	93–93.3m	93–93.5m	2011	32.86096524	24.23571709
48DF	93.099	93–93.3m	93–93.5m	2011	32.86084403	24.23570807
48BC	93.010	93–93.3m	93–93.5m	2011	32.86068171	24.23572932
47FF	92.911	92–93m	92.5–93m	2011	32.86054732	24.23576753
470A	92.826	92–93m	92.5–93m	2011	32.86049809	24.23576416
47F8	92.552	92–93m	92.5–93m	2011	32.86049156	24.23568401
48C3	92.520	92–93m	92.5–93m	2011	32.8605691	24.23557443
486F	92.743	92–93m	92.5–93m	2011	32.8607191	24.23561355
48D8	92.611	92–93m	92.5–93m	2011	32.86076363	24.23557997
4964	92.671	92–93m	92.5–93m	2011	32.860905	24.23563731
499C	92.987	92–93m	92.5–93m	2011	32.86103949	24.23558677
4B0E	92.722	92–93m	92.5–93m	2011	32.86078206	24.23554355
496B	92.295	92–93m	92–92.5m	2011	32.86083225	24.23553077
4972	92.393	92–93m	92–92.5m	2011	32.86076235	24.23543177
498E	92.157	92–93m	92–92.5m	2011	32.86093448	24.23546489
4A2F	92.194	92–93m	92–92.5m	2011	32.86102671	24.23542652
4A75	92.115	92–93m	92–92.5m	2011	32.86109922	24.23543017
4995	92.366	92–93m	92–92.5m	2011	32.86098125	24.23552902

TABLE 2 Elevation points from the area of the Predynastic village of Nag el-Qarmila (wk15). (cont.)

Name	Elev	Range	Range2	Year	xcoord	ycoord
4A28	92.498	92–93m	92–92.5m	2011	32.86107868	24.23548645
4A7C	91.889	< 92m	< 92m	2011	32.86113135	24.23548092
4A21	92.431	92–93m	92–92.5m	2011	32.86112106	24.23553212
4A1A	91.797	< 92m	< 92m	2011	32.86113897	24.23554449
4A83	91.597	< 92m	< 92m	2011	32.86118596	24.23554442

bailer boring equipment was used for drilling below the water table (a stainless-steel tube with a stainless-steel valve on the lower part). By moving the bailer rapidly up and down, loose water-filled material was collected in the bailer. To prevent the collapse of the drilling hole, synthetic casing tubes were lowered as the bailer proceeded. Colors were determined on wet (at field capacity) sediments using the Revised Standard Soil Color Charts (Fujihara Industry Co. 1970, 2001). The X- and Y- position of each observation point was

FIGURE 6 Nag el-Qarmila village WK15, the spatial location of elevation points.

FIGURE 7 Nag el-Qarmila, spatial distribution of drill cores from 2007, 2009, and 2011.

originally measured by a hand-held GPS navigator (Garmin GPS 12XL) in UTM-coordinates on the ‘Old Egyptian’ map datum (2007) and WGS 84 map datum (2009–2011). They are here reported in WGS 84/UTM Zone 36 N map datum for consistency. An estimation of the accuracy of the averaged position was given by the FOM (Figure of Merit)-value expressed in meters. The X- and Y-position and the altitude Z of major observation points were measured more precisely using a total station. As zero-level for the Z-measurements, the water level of the Nile near the site and on the day of the measurement was chosen. It was estimated in 2007 at 84.00 m a.s.l., considering the water level of the Nilometer at Aswan was 85.20 m a.s.l. on the day of the measurement (13.02.2007) and a drop of 1.20 m over the distance of 17 km between Aswan and Nag el-Qarmila (the mean drop of the Nile level was calculated to be about 70 mm/km). For our argument, we report the unpublished details of the observation points done in 2007 and 2009, while we only mention two from 2011 (Table 3).

The number of observation points in 2007 was limited to 12 but allowed for a preliminary interpretation, which is illustrated by a 370 m-long NNE-SSW profile across the wadi valley (Fig. 8) and by a panoramic view of the landscape (Fig. 2). According to De Dapper (in Gatto et al. 2009b:187–190):

The wadi valley is completely eroded in a plateau consisting of a bedrock of fluvial sandstone belonging to the Upper Cretaceous ‘Umm Barmil Formation’ (Kub). The sandstone is exposed on both wadi valley sides. The northern valley side is a simple rectilinear slope. The southern valley

TABLE 3 Information from the drill cores (from AKAP Archives, based on interim reports by De Dapper).

Drilling Number	Date	Intervals	Description	Geological Formation	Chronology	Surface Observation	Elevation	X coordinate	Y coordinate
1	13-02-07	\	Slope in purplish fluvialite sandstone	'Umm Barmil Formation' (Kub)	Upper Cretaceous	QUB/N/07/006	102.98 m asl	32.86119541	24.236662595
2	13-02-07	\	Distinct concave slope change; limit between rocky sandstone slope and Middle-Pleistocene river terrace; lag of Ca-carbonate root casts at the surface	\	\	QUB/N/07/005	98.66 m asl	32.86117105	24.23652735
3	12-02-07	0-110 cm	Medium sand; yellow; homogeneous. Abundant Ca-carbonate root casts	River terrace	Middle-Pleistocene	QUB/N/07/002	97.18 m asl	32.86117065	24.23624626
4	12-02-07	\	Concave slope change; lower limit of Middle-Pleistocene river terrace	\	\	QUB/N/07/004	96.56 m asl	32.8610078	24.23611856
5	13-02-07	20-110 cm	Medium to fine sand; yellow; homogeneous. Few subrounded-rounded red sandstone gravels, up to 1 cm diameter. Few Ca-carbonate root casts	River terrace	Middle-Pleistocene	QUB/N/07/011	95.36 m asl	32.86106402	24.23596256

TABLE 3 Information from the drill cores (from akap Archives, based on interim reports by De Dapper). (cont.)

Drilling Number	Date	Intervals	Description	Geological Formation	Chronology	Surface Observation	Elevation	X coordinate	Y coordinate
6	12-02-07	0-30 cm	Medium sand; yellow; homogeneous	Aeolian	(Sub)recent				
		30-50 cm	Silty medium sand; gray to yellow; sandstone flake of 5 cm diameter at 50 cm	Anthropogenic mixed layer		QUB/N/07/001	93.96 m asl	32.8611062	24.23569372
		50-85 cm	Fine sandy silt; gray black; homogeneous; very compact; very hard when dry	'Wild Nile' flood silt	Late Pleistocene/Early Holocene				
7	13-02-07	0-35 cm	Medium sand; yellow; homogeneous	Aeolian	(Sub)recent				
		35-55 cm	Silty medium sand; gray to yellow	Anthropogenic mixed layer					
		55-85 cm	Fine sandy silt; gray black; homogeneous; very compact; very hard when dry	'Wild Nile' flood silt	Late Pleistocene/Early Holocene	QUB/N/07/007	93.50 m asl	32.86102828	24.23568128
		0-20 cm	Medium sand; yellow; homogeneous	Aeolian	(Sub)recent				

TABLE 3 Information from the drill cores (from akap Archives, based on interim reports by De Dapper). (cont.)

Drilling Number	Date	Intervals	Description	Geological Formation	Chronology	Surface Observation	Elevation	X coordinate	Y coordinate
8	13-02-07	20-40 cm	Silty medium sand; gray to yellow	Anthropogenic mixed layer					
		40-50 cm	Fine sandy silt; gray black; homogeneous; very compact; very hard when dry	'Wild Nile' flood silt	Late Pleistocene/ Early Holocene		92.43 m asl	32.86101013	24.23562097
		0-30 cm	Medium sand; yellow; homogeneous	Aeolian	(Sub)recent				
9	13-02-07	30-40 cm	Silty medium sand; gray to yellow	Anthropogenic mixed layer					
		40-50 cm	Fine sandy silt; gray black; homogeneous; very compact; very hard when dry	'Wild Nile' flood silt	Late Pleistocene/ Early Holocene	QUB/N/07/009	92.95 m asl	32.86089678	24.23549172
10	13-02-07	0-10 cm	Medium sand mixed with stone rubble	Anthropogenic	Recent				
		10-40 cm	Medium sand; yellow; homogeneous	Aeolian	(Sub)recent				
		40-50 cm	Silty medium sand; gray to yellow. Charcoal fragments at 50 cm	Anthropogenic mixed layer					

TABLE 3 Information from the drill cores (from akap Archives, based on interim reports by De Dapper). (cont.)

Drilling Number	Date	Intervals	Description	Geological Formation	Chronology	Surface Observation	Elevation	X coordinate	Y coordinate
		50–70 cm	Fine sandy silt; gray black; homogeneous; very compact; very hard when dry	'Wild Nile' flood silt	Late Pleistocene/Early Holocene	QUB/N/07/001	93.02 m asl	32.86080369	24.23542215
		0–30 cm	Medium sand; yellow; homogeneous	Aeolian	(Sub)recent				
		30–110 cm	Slightly silty medium sand; yellow brown; homogeneous. Fragment of Ca-carbonate root cast of 5 cm diameter at 100 cm						
		110–120 cm	Medium to coarse sand; yellow brown; homogeneous	Wadi alluvial deposits	Subrecent				
		120–130 cm	Silty fine to medium sand; brown; homogeneous						
		130–240 cm	Silty medium to coarse sand; brown; homogeneous. Few sandstone gravels of 1 cm diameter						

TABLE 3 Information from the drill cores (from akap Archives, based on interim reports by De Dapper). (cont.)

Drilling Number	Date	Intervals	Description	Geological Formation	Chronology	Surface Observation	Elevation	X coordinate	Y coordinate
II	12-13/02/2007	240-320 cm	Slightly medium sandy silt; gray; white Ca-carbonate stains; Mn-stains. Subangular sandstone gravel of 5 cm diameter at 280 cm			QUB/N/07/003	92.93 m asl	32.86043998	24.2354148
		320-390 cm	Slightly silty fine to medium sand to fine to medium sandy silt; yellow brown; homogeneous. Angular sandstone fragment of 1 cm diameter at 340 cm	Nile floodplain deposits with interfingering of wadi alluvial deposits	Late Holocene				
		390-450 cm	Fine to medium sandy silt to silty fine to medium sand; gray brown; Ca-carbonate stains. Waterable at 400 cm						
		450-535 cm	Medium to coarse sand; yellow brown; homogeneous. Few gravel of up to 1 cm diameter	River terrace	Middle-Pleistocene				
		535 cm	Bedrock	Bedrock	/				

TABLE 3 Information from the drill cores (from akap Archives, based on interim reports by De Dapper). (cont.)

Drilling Number	Date	Intervals	Description	Geological Formation	Chronology	Surface Observation	Elevation	X coordinate	Y coordinate
12	14-02-07	\	Structural terrace in fluvial sandstone. Differential abrasion on sandstone.	'Umm Barmil Formation' (Kub)	Upper Cretaceous	QUB/N/07/012	101.03 m asl	32.85916942	24.23444965
		0-230 cm	Medium to fine sand; 10YR 6/6 (bright yellowish brown); homogeneous; very few subangular rock fragments of up to 5 mm diameter.	Aeolian	\				
13	12-11-09	230-300 cm 300-400 cm	Sharp boundary. Fine sandy silt to silty fine sand; 10YR 5/3 (dull yellowish brown); abundant micas; homogeneous	Fluvial (flood-plain facies)	Holocene	QUB/N/09/013	93.85 m asl	32.86075474	24.23588812
		300-400 cm	Transition. Slightly fine sandy silt; 10YR 4/3 (dull yellowish brown); homogeneous; at - 350 cm: subangular rock fragment of 1.5 cm diameter	Fluvial (flood-plain facies)	Holocene				

TABLE 3 Information from the drill cores (from akap Archives, based on interim reports by De Dapper). (cont.)

Drilling Number	Date	Intervals	Description	Geological Formation	Chronology	Surface Observation	Elevation	X coordinate	Y coordinate
14	12-11-09	(400 cm)	Sharp boundary. Few rounded pebbles, up to 1 cm diameter; hard surface	Fluvial-wadi on bedrock					
		0-180 cm	Very fine to fine sand; 10YR 5/6 (yellowish brown); homogeneous; at - 30 cm: Nagada sherd (1.5 cm diameter); at - 70 cm: Nagada Ic sherd (3 cm diameter)	Local aeolian deposit					
		180-300 cm	Sharp boundary. Silty medium sand to medium sandy silt; 10YR 4/4 (brown); homogeneous; very few subangular gravels of up to 2 cm diameter	Fluvial (flood-plain facies)	Holocene	QUB/N/09/016	92.74 m asl	32.86069893	24.2356671
		300-400 cm	Transition. Medium to coarse sand; 10YR 4/4 (brown); homogeneous; few subangular to subrounded gravels of up to 2 cm diameter	Fluvial (wadi facies)	Holocene				

TABLE 3 Information from the drill cores (from akap Archives, based on interim reports by De Dapper). (cont.)

Drilling Number	Date	Intervals	Description	Geological Formation	Chronology	Surface Observation	Elevation	X coordinate	Y coordinate
24	16-20/01/2011	(400 cm)	Sharp boundary. Hard surface	Bedrock					
			Fluvial material from of the outer part of the Wadi was found topped with layer of Nile sediments, most probably the transition zone between the Wild Nile terrace and the valley of the Wadi				92.76 m asl	32.86052081	24.23579665
25	16-20/01/2011		Wild Nile terrace	Wild Nile terrace					
		88.20m	Hard surface	Bedrock			93.43 m asl	32.86053702	24.23587923

FIGURE 8 Nag el-Qarmila, 370 m-long NNE-SSW profile across the valley (revised after De Dapper in Gatto et al. 2009b, Fig. 4).

side is more complex: two rectilinear slope segments are separated by a very gently sloping structural rock terrace. The lower part of this terrace is marked by an outspoken convex slope change. The alluvial fill of the valley bottom is only a few meters thick and comprises different lithostratigraphical units. The oldest unit is formed by a Middle-Pleistocene river terrace composed of medium sandy sediments. In the upper part abundant root casts, formed by the infilling of Ca-carbonate in former root tubes, are present in situ. The incision of the Middle-Pleistocene valley bottom sediments took place in the southern part of the valley bottom. As a result, the Middle-Pleistocene river terrace was only developed at the foot of the northern valley slope. The younger sediments comprise an up to 2 m thick and very hard layer of dark, compact silts which were deposited by the catastrophic floods of the ‘Wild Nile’ stage at the transition of Late Pleistocene/Holocene. The compact silt layer is topped by a layer of mixed silt and sand with a thickness of a few tens of cm; the

presence of charcoal and sandstone flakes testifies of an anthropogenic origin. The present-day valley bottom is situated in the southern part of the wadi valley. It is separated from the southern rocky valley slope by a concave slope change and filled by Holocene alluvial sediments comprising two distinct units. The lower one, below the actual Nile floodplain level (at 91,34 m a.s.l.) is composed of mainly Nile floodplain silts inter-fingered with thin layers of fine to medium sand; the silts were deposited during the yearly Nile floods while the sands are wadi sediments deposited during the rare winter rains. The sediments above the actual Nile floodplain level are exclusively coarse to medium sandy wadi deposits; the presence of sandstone and root-cast fragments shows they are the result of the erosion of the rocky valley slopes and the Middle-Pleistocene river terrace. The whole landscape is covered by a discontinuous veneer of yellow medium sand. This sandy layer is the result of persistent aeolian activity. The major sand source is the Middle-Pleistocene river terrace. The aeolian activity is corroborated by the presence of a lag of root cast fragments on top of the terrace. Differential wind abrasion on the rocky valley slopes is another proof of important and persistent aeolian activity.

In 2009, only two cores (nos. 13–14) were drilled at Nag el-Qarmila, west of those made in 2007 and of the settlement (see Fig. 6 for location). They both were instrumental in reconsidering the previously underestimated thickness of the aeolian sand covering part of the northern terrace and the Predynastic sites (De Dapper 2009). Among the observation points of 2011, two are worth mentioning (nos. 24 and 25) because they changed the original assessment and reduced the Wild Nile deposit's extension in the wadi's inner part (see Fig. 2).

In De Dapper's interpretation (in Gatto et al. 2009b:189–190), the thalweg of the alluvial valley bottom was likely between 2 and 3 m deeper than it is now. Therefore, it was affected by the yearly Nile flood. Furthermore, the aquifer in the sandy silt of the lower alluvial infill was recharged on a regular base by the Nile flood, as was occasionally the case by winter rains. Consequently, the water table reached close to the surface throughout the year. For that reason, the inhabitants of Nag el-Qarmila could take advantage of aquatic resources beyond just the inundation season. Thus, there is less pressure to situate ephemeral dwellings to maximize resource consumption. This fact provides a good argument in favor of the long-term use of the settlement. However, and this supports the archaeological record, De Dapper, in his reconstruction of the geomorphology of the valley, never mentions any Predynastic alluvial deposit covering or intermingling with the anthropic deposits of the settlement, providing for the first time, sound evidence for early 4th millennium high

inundation levels to be lower than expected from currently available proxy data (discussed below in section 4).

4 Archaeological and Historical Documentation Related to Nile Floods

Beyond the archaeological evidence and the drill cores detailed above, we are fortunate to have a variety of archaeological proxies and historical records that document Nile flooding in the Aswan region with varying degrees of precision from the early 20th century all the way back to the late 4th millennium BCE. However, of paramount concern to us is whether the average Nile flood during the Naqada I through early Naqada III/Dynasty Zero was higher or lower than during the Naqada IIIC-Naqada IIID/1st–2nd Dynasties. For this period, unfortunately, we have confusing information. In fact, on the one hand, evidence is reported of reduced river flow and channel contraction at c. 4400–4140 BCE, based on low water levels in Lake Victoria and Lake Tana and decreasing flow in the Nile Delta, and at c. 3700–3450 BCE, based on falling water levels in Lake Victoria and Lake Fayum (Macklin et al. 2015:116). On the other hand, drill cores from the Saqqara region suggest relatively high floods during this period (Hassan et al. 2017), and Bunbury and Rowe note the apparent variability in Nile floods even as the aridification of the Sahara encouraged settlement closer to the Nile and its major wadis (Bunbury & Rowe 2021:9–19).

During the earlier 4th millennium BCE, and therefore during the period of greatest relevance for this study, there is a relative lacuna in terms of archaeological sequences or environmental proxy data from the First Cataract region itself beyond the results documented by the drill cores taken by the German Archaeological Institute and AKAP. In the rare instances where fossilized river channels have been investigated in Lower Nubia (Zaki et al. 2021), the data conforms to sediment analyses from the Nile's deep-sea fan (Ménot et al. 2020; Revel et al. 2015) and archaeological sequences further south at Kerma (Honegger & Williams 2015), suggesting the terminal phases of the *African Humid Period* (c. 5300 BCE–3500 BCE) affected the climate of the First Cataract region during the 4th millennium BCE (Zaki et al. 2021).⁵ It is accepted that flood levels during this period were likely slightly higher on average than in subsequent periods but did not approach the extreme highs from 8500 BCE to 5300 BCE. However, as noted above, the geo-archaeological data from Nag el-Qarmila does not support this theory. In sum, based on current

⁵ See also the studies in Woodward et al. 2015, more generally.

scholarship, it is not possible at this juncture to precisely specify the extent of flooding during much of the 4th millennium BCE. Moreover, there is limited proxy data from the region near Aswan with which to model flooding in the region until the advent of the Dynastic Period when the increasingly dense settlement at Elephantine allows for more reliable conjectures. Our data from Nag el-Qarmila (but also from the settlement of Nag el-Tawil), which points to a similar flood elevation to that of the late 4th–early 3rd millennium, is the only one available at this point. We owe Stephan Seidlmayer an enormous debt of gratitude for his 2001 monograph that meticulously parses the archaeological evidence from Elephantine as well as historical records from the Pharaonic and especially the Islamic period.⁶ Flood levels at Elephantine are estimated based on the lowest elevations with settlement or copious amounts of occupational debris from a given time period (Seidlmayer 2001:90). The Nile flooding seems to have declined from quite high levels during the First Dynasty (c.3100–2850 BCE), with an average maximum height of roughly 94.50–94.00 m a.s.l., to approximately 92.50–92.00 m a.s.l. by the time of the construction of the Elephantine town wall during the 2nd Dynasty (Ziermann in Kaiser et al. 1995:138–140). Nile floods seem to have further decreased after the Early Dynastic Period. After perhaps rising slightly during the 4th Dynasty, inundations declined to an average maximum height of about 91.30–90.80 m a.s.l. by the 6th Dynasty before rising somewhat during the First Intermediate Period (Seidlmayer 2001:81–92). During this time, the town at Elephantine gradually expanded, and the gap between the Western and Eastern islands was infilled and settled. During the later Old Kingdom, there may even have been some efforts to create a dam or at least an effort to protect some of the lower, more vulnerable occupied areas from the vicissitudes of the Nile flood (Ziermann in Kaiser et al. 1995:131–136). The situation for the earlier periods covered by this study is far murkier: occupation at Elephantine was less dense in the periods before the Early Dynastic (Kopp 2006), and there remains the possibility that more ephemeral dwellings at lower elevations were washed away by high Nile inundations.

Although sporadic Nilometer readings known throughout the Pharaonic period allow scholars to estimate relative fluctuations in Nile inundations, the quality of these readings markedly increased during Late Antiquity and the Medieval period. Islamic historians documented the maximum height of the annual inundation at the Nilometer at Rawda (Cairo) as far back as 622 CE. The historian Ibn Taghribirdī documented yearly flood levels at Rawda

6 Seidlmayer (2001). Indeed, this remains the definitive source on historical Nile flooding data.

in cubits from 641 to 1469 CE, and his efforts provided the core of this data set (Ibn Taghribirdi, translated in Popper 1954). Later scholars like Omar Toussoun (1925) and William Popper (1951) analyzed Ibn Taghribirdi figures, translated them into the metric system, and introduced accounts from additional Islamic scholars to extend this record of Nile inundation data back to 622 CE and up to the early 20th century, though there are notable periods during the late 15th to 18th centuries where data is lacking (cf. Toussoun 1925:390–404; Popper 1951).

There is information on maximum Nile heights for approximately 1081 of the 1277 inundations between 622 CE and the construction of the Aswan Low Dam in 1898. For the years between 1869 and 1898, before the beginning of this dam's construction, there is data both from Rawda as well as water gauges near Aswan and Wadi Halfa (Seidlmayer 2001:109–111). The gauge readings from 1869–1898 show that the mean 10-day maximum height of the Nile flood was usually 8–9 m higher than the mean 10-day minimum height of the river during the dry season (Seidlmayer 2001:110). After the construction of the Aswan Low Dam, the maximum flood levels at Aswan had to be extrapolated based on readings from other sources. The gauge at nearby Wadi Halfa continued to be reliable through the 1925 inundation, but in the following years, irrigation projects further upstream contributed to a decreasing water level and rendered these readings less reliable (Seidlmayer 2001:109). The hydrologist Harold Edwin Hurst's efforts in the intervening years allowed for the reconstruction of maximum Nile levels near Aswan through 1967, though this is, of course, based on proxy data.⁷ Together, these historical accounts and water gauge readings provide the world's longest sequence of inundation records. Seidlmayer also engaged with these published Islamic sources on Nile heights, and his work provides the basis for our modelling of the floodplain near Aswan, detailed in the following section of this article (Seidlmayer 2001:106–121). For our purposes, Seidlmayer's key insight was the realization that there were readings from Rawda and Aswan between 1869 and 1898. Seidlmayer performed a linear regression to determine the relationship between these values over these 30 years, finding that the maximum height of the Nile at Rawda 'R' in meters above sea level is approximately equal to 1.240388 multiplied by the Aswan gauge reading 'A' minus 95.75; thus, the equation $R = 1.240388 * (A) - 95.75$ (Seidlmayer 2001:113–114). This can be easily manipulated to estimate the maximum Nile height at Aswan during the periods where only a figure from Rawda was recorded: $A = (R + 95.75) / 1.240388$. This allows for an imperfect estimate of Nile

7 In general, see Hurst (1931); for relevant supplements detailing gauge data, see Hurst & Phillips/Nile Control Staff (1933–1967).

flood levels at Aswan for much of the last 1400 years, as shown in Table 4. This corpus of maximum inundation heights is robust enough to allow for basic statistical modelling within GIS software that can approximate one in one-hundred or one in one-thousand-year weather events: in this case, particularly high inundations that perhaps come relatively closer to approximating the higher average flood levels from the 4th millennium BCE. More importantly, such efforts also allow for AKAP's geophysical and archaeological data to be considered in tandem with spatial modelling.

4.1 *Limitations and Creation of the Model*

This limited model is only useful in combination with information from archaeological sequences or drill cores that provide direct evidence of the paleo-landscape: our intent is not to uncritically equate environmental conditions from the previous 1500 years with those of the 4th millennium BCE. Beyond artificially induced changes to the landscape, there is every reason to suspect that changing climactic regimes affected both the volume and severity of the annual inundation. The balance of evidence suggests that it is probable that the terminal phases of the *African Humid Period* witnessed incrementally higher floods than subsequent periods (Woodward et al. 2015). For the Dynastic period, contemporary records can be combined with archaeological stratigraphy or drill cores to help get a sense of maximum flood levels. However, for the 4th millennium BCE, as detailed above, there is no textual data, and current understandings of flood levels have relied heavily on environmental proxy data or archaeological sequences from Nubia or north of the First Cataract region. The paucity of environmental (Zaki et al. 2021) or archaeological forays (like AKAP's efforts detailed above) relevant for assessing Nile heights during this timeframe allows for estimates but not more robust modelling. Thus, despite the model's deficiencies, we prefer to make use of the unparalleled inundation records from Rawda to supplement and contextualize the archaeological and geophysical data from our study region presented in this paper.

We wish to acknowledge several additional weaknesses of our floodplain modelling: most obviously, there is only a small series of values where data from Aswan and Rawda can be directly compared (in years 1869–1898) and extrapolating via a best-fit line to the entire chronological span undoubtedly introduces some additional error. Beyond this, there is the possibility of slight errors in the figures from Rawda as a result of the changing size of the cubit or the techniques of measurement over the course of the 7th–15th century CE. These potential issues are discussed and addressed by Omar Toussoun (1925) and especially William Popper (1951), so there is little reason to doubt

TABLE 4 Historical inundation data used for the flooding model.

Year	Maximum at Roda	Recalculated Maximum at Aswan Based on Roda	Known Maximum Aswan	Average 10 Day Minima Aswan	Average 10 Day Maxima Aswan
622	16.88	90.80223285	\	\	\
623	16.52	90.51200108	\	\	\
624	16.98	90.88285278	\	\	\
625	16.69	90.64905497	\	\	\
626	16.75	90.69742693	\	\	\
627	17.63	91.40688236	\	\	\
628	16.83	90.76192288	\	\	\
629	15.65	89.81060765	\	\	\
630	16.63	90.60068301	\	\	\
631	16.65	90.616807	\	\	\
632	16.06	90.14114938	\	\	\
633	18.51	92.11633779	\	\	\
634	17.27	91.1166506	\	\	\
635	18.21	91.87447799	\	\	\
636	17.69	91.45525432	\	\	\
637	17.31	91.14889857	\	\	\
638	16.5	90.4958771	\	\	\
639	17.61	91.39075838	\	\	\
640	16.77	90.71355092	\	\	\
641	17.34	91.17308455	\	\	\
642	17.04	90.93122475	\	\	\
643	16.83	90.76192288	\	\	\
644	16.71	90.66517896	\	\	\
645	16.6	90.57649703	\	\	\
646	17.04	90.93122475	\	\	\
647	16.56	90.54424906	\	\	\

TABLE 4 Historical inundation data used for the flooding model. (*cont.*)

Year	Maximum at Roda	Recalculated Maximum at Aswan Based on Roda	Known Maximum Aswan	Average 10 Day Minima Aswan	Average 10 Day Maxima Aswan
648	16.77	90.71355092	\	\	\
649	17.86	91.59230821	\	\	\
650	16.83	90.76192288	\	\	\
651	15.95	90.05246745	\	\	\
652	16.25	90.29432726	\	\	\
653	17.11	90.9876587	\	\	\
654	16.25	90.29432726	\	\	\
655	16.98	90.88285278	\	\	\
656	17.44	91.25370449	\	\	\
657	16.54	90.52812507	\	\	\
658	16.65	90.616807	\	\	\
659	16.58	90.56037304	\	\	\
660	17.71	91.47137831	\	\	\
661	17.53	91.32626243	\	\	\
662	17.04	90.93122475	\	\	\
663	17.04	90.93122475	\	\	\
664	17.42	91.2375805	\	\	\
665	16.58	90.56037304	\	\	\
666	16.65	90.616807	\	\	\
667	16.61	90.58455903	\	\	\
668	17.44	91.25370449	\	\	\
669	16.6	90.57649703	\	\	\
670	16.56	90.54424906	\	\	\
671	18.3	91.94703593	\	\	\
672	16.87	90.79417086	\	\	\
673	16.56	90.54424906	\	\	\

TABLE 4 Historical inundation data used for the flooding model. (*cont.*)

Year	Maximum at Roda	Recalculated Maximum at Aswan Based on Roda	Known Maximum Aswan	Average 10 Day Minima Aswan	Average 10 Day Maxima Aswan
674	16.63	90.60068301	\	\	\
675	16.6	90.57649703	\	\	\
676	16.52	90.51200108	\	\	\
677	16.77	90.71355092	\	\	\
678	16.23	90.27820327	\	\	\
679	17.15	91.01990667	\	\	\
680	17	90.89897677	\	\	\
681	17.02	90.91510076	\	\	\
682	17.02	90.91510076	\	\	\
683	16.56	90.54424906	\	\	\
684	17.07	90.95541073	\	\	\
685	16.77	90.71355092	\	\	\
686	16.52	90.51200108	\	\	\
687	16.77	90.71355092	\	\	\
688	15.21	89.45587993	\	\	\
689	16.88	90.80223285	\	\	\
690	16.39	90.40719517	\	\	\
691	16.39	90.40719517	\	\	\
692	17	90.89897677	\	\	\
693	15.84	89.96378553	\	\	\
694	15.26	89.4961899	\	\	\
695	15.68	89.83479363	\	\	\
696	15.42	89.6251818	\	\	\
697	17.33	91.16502256	\	\	\
698	17.73	91.4875023	\	\	\
699	17.27	91.1166506	\	\	\

TABLE 4 Historical inundation data used for the flooding model. (*cont.*)

Year	Maximum at Roda	Recalculated Maximum at Aswan Based on Roda	Known Maximum Aswan	Average 10 Day Minima Aswan	Average 10 Day Maxima Aswan
700	17.09	90.97153471	\	\	\
701	16.81	90.7457989	\	\	\
702	16.42	90.43138115	\	\	\
703	17.34	91.17308455	\	\	\
704	16.88	90.80223285	\	\	\
705	15.44	89.64130578	\	\	\
706	16.87	90.79417086	\	\	\
707	16.87	90.79417086	\	\	\
708	17.36	91.18920854	\	\	\
709	16.9	90.81835684	\	\	\
710	16.81	90.7457989	\	\	\
711	17.13	91.00378269	\	\	\
712	16.87	90.79417086	\	\	\
713	15.57	89.7461117	\	\	\
714	17.17	91.03603066	\	\	\
715	17.33	91.16502256	\	\	\
716	17.04	90.93122475	\	\	\
717	17.06	90.94734873	\	\	\
718	17.33	91.16502256	\	\	\
719	17.82	91.56006024	\	\	\
720	17.82	91.56006024	\	\	\
721	17.52	91.31820043	\	\	\
722	16.23	90.27820327	\	\	\
723	17.27	91.1166506	\	\	\
724	17.48	91.28595246	\	\	\
725	16.98	90.88285278	\	\	\

TABLE 4 Historical inundation data used for the flooding model. (*cont.*)

Year	Maximum at Roda	Recalculated Maximum at Aswan Based on Roda	Known Maximum Aswan	Average 10 Day Minima Aswan	Average 10 Day Maxima Aswan
726	16.1	90.17339736	\	\	\
727	17.04	90.93122475	\	\	\
728	17.25	91.10052661	\	\	\
729	17.25	91.10052661	\	\	\
730	16.81	90.7457989	\	\	\
731	17.4	91.22145651	\	\	\
732	17.33	91.16502256	\	\	\
733	15.94	90.04440546	\	\	\
734	15.75	89.89122758	\	\	\
735	15.94	90.04440546	\	\	\
736	16.87	90.79417086	\	\	\
737	16.14	90.20564533	\	\	\
738	16.53	90.52006308	\	\	\
739	16.73	90.68130295	\	\	\
740	16.37	90.39107118	\	\	\
741	17.65	91.42300635	\	\	\
742	17.65	91.42300635	\	\	\
743	16.73	90.68130295	\	\	\
744	17.17	91.03603066	\	\	\
745	17.17	91.03603066	\	\	\
746	16.5	90.4958771	\	\	\
747	16.73	90.68130295	\	\	\
748	16.57	90.55231105	\	\	\
749	16.56	90.54424906	\	\	\
750	16.5	90.4958771	\	\	\
751	17.57	91.3585104	\	\	\

TABLE 4 Historical inundation data used for the flooding model. (*cont.*)

Year	Maximum at Roda	Recalculated Maximum at Aswan Based on Roda	Known Maximum Aswan	Average 10 Day Minima Aswan	Average 10 Day Maxima Aswan
752	17.59	91.37463439	\	\	\
753	16.54	90.52812507	\	\	\
754	17.52	91.31820043	\	\	\
755	17.07	90.95541073	\	\	\
756	15.94	90.04440546	\	\	\
757	16.87	90.79417086	\	\	\
758	16.63	90.60068301	\	\	\
759	16.27	90.31045125	\	\	\
760	17.13	91.00378269	\	\	\
761	16.25	90.29432726	\	\	\
762	16.29	90.32657523	\	\	\
763	16.33	90.35882321	\	\	\
764	15.92	90.02828147	\	\	\
765	16.33	90.35882321	\	\	\
766	16.64	90.60874501	\	\	\
767	16.41	90.42331915	\	\	\
768	16.79	90.72967491	\	\	\
769	16.05	90.13308739	\	\	\
770	17.13	91.00378269	\	\	\
771	16.31	90.34269922	\	\	\
772	16.37	90.39107118	\	\	\
773	16.44	90.44750514	\	\	\
774	17.33	91.16502256	\	\	\
775	16.99	90.89091478	\	\	\
776	16.06	90.14114938	\	\	\
777	16.48	90.47975311	\	\	\

TABLE 4 Historical inundation data used for the flooding model. (*cont.*)

Year	Maximum at Roda	Recalculated Maximum at Aswan Based on Roda	Known Maximum Aswan	Average 10 Day Minima Aswan	Average 10 Day Maxima Aswan
778	17.48	91.28595246	\	\	\
779	16.25	90.29432726	\	\	\
780	16.31	90.34269922	\	\	\
781	16.31	90.34269922	\	\	\
782	15.57	89.7461117	\	\	\
783	16.96	90.8667288	\	\	\
784	16.83	90.76192288	\	\	\
785	16.31	90.34269922	\	\	\
786	17.23	91.08440262	\	\	\
787	17.33	91.16502256	\	\	\
788	16.07	90.14921138	\	\	\
789	16.08	90.15727337	\	\	\
790	17.1	90.97959671	\	\	\
791	15.9	90.01215749	\	\	\
792	16.33	90.35882321	\	\	\
793	16.79	90.72967491	\	\	\
794	16.33	90.35882321	\	\	\
795	17.13	91.00378269	\	\	\
796	16.19	90.2459553	\	\	\
797	17.1	90.97959671	\	\	\
798	16.94	90.85060481	\	\	\
799	15.99	90.08471543	\	\	\
800	17.02	90.91510076	\	\	\
801	17.07	90.95541073	\	\	\
802	15.97	90.06859144	\	\	\
803	15.59	89.76223569	\	\	\

TABLE 4 Historical inundation data used for the flooding model. (*cont.*)

Year	Maximum at Roda	Recalculated Maximum at Aswan Based on Roda	Known Maximum Aswan	Average 10 Day Minima Aswan	Average 10 Day Maxima Aswan
804	17.13	91.00378269	\	\	\
805	16.98	90.88285278	\	\	\
806	17.07	90.95541073	\	\	\
807	17.07	90.95541073	\	\	\
808	17.25	91.10052661	\	\	\
809	16.79	90.72967491	\	\	\
810	17.23	91.08440262	\	\	\
811	16.43	90.43944314	\	\	\
812	17.06	90.94734873	\	\	\
813	17.17	91.03603066	\	\	\
814	17.04	90.93122475	\	\	\
815	17.15	91.01990667	\	\	\
816	17.27	91.1166506	\	\	\
817	15.9	90.01215749	\	\	\
818	16.39	90.40719517	\	\	\
819	16.58	90.56037304	\	\	\
820	17.21	91.06827864	\	\	\
821	17.29	91.13277458	\	\	\
822	16.81	90.7457989	\	\	\
823	17.29	91.13277458	\	\	\
824	17.29	91.13277458	\	\	\
825	17.29	91.13277458	\	\	\
826	17.09	90.97153471	\	\	\
827	17.07	90.95541073	\	\	\
828	16.32	90.35076121	\	\	\
829	16.87	90.79417086	\	\	\

TABLE 4 Historical inundation data used for the flooding model. (*cont.*)

Year	Maximum at Roda	Recalculated Maximum at Aswan Based on Roda	Known Maximum Aswan	Average 10 Day Minima Aswan	Average 10 Day Maxima Aswan
830	15.49	89.68161575	\	\	\
831	16.21	90.26207928	\	\	\
832	15.67	89.82673164	\	\	\
833	16.02	90.10890141	\	\	\
834	16.22	90.27014128	\	\	\
835	16.82	90.75386089	\	\	\
836	16.89	90.81029484	\	\	\
837	15.97	90.06859144	\	\	\
838	16.93	90.84254282	\	\	\
839	15.19	89.43975595	\	\	\
840	16.87	90.79417086	\	\	\
841	15.67	89.82673164	\	\	\
842	16.65	90.616807	\	\	\
843	16.6	90.57649703	\	\	\
844	16.65	90.616807	\	\	\
845	16.65	90.616807	\	\	\
846	17.01	90.90703877	\	\	\
847	16.33	90.35882321	\	\	\
848	16.87	90.79417086	\	\	\
849	16.44	90.44750514	\	\	\
850	16.41	90.42331915	\	\	\
851	17.17	91.03603066	\	\	\
852	16.31	90.34269922	\	\	\
853	16.92	90.83448082	\	\	\
854	17.17	91.03603066	\	\	\
855	17.04	90.93122475	\	\	\

TABLE 4 Historical inundation data used for the flooding model. (*cont.*)

Year	Maximum at Roda	Recalculated Maximum at Aswan Based on Roda	Known Maximum Aswan	Average 10 Day Minima Aswan	Average 10 Day Maxima Aswan
856	17.04	90.93122475	\	\	\
857	16.98	90.88285278	\	\	\
858	16.71	90.66517896	\	\	\
859	16.54	90.52812507	\	\	\
860	16.87	90.79417086	\	\	\
861	17.21	91.06827864	\	\	\
862	17.31	91.14889857	\	\	\
863	17.15	91.01990667	\	\	\
864	17.23	91.08440262	\	\	\
865	17.09	90.97153471	\	\	\
866	17.36	91.18920854	\	\	\
867	17.13	91.00378269	\	\	\
868	16.79	90.72967491	\	\	\
869	17.06	90.94734873	\	\	\
870	16.48	90.47975311	\	\	\
871	17.29	91.13277458	\	\	\
872	16.59	90.56843504	\	\	\
873	16.59	90.56843504	\	\	\
874	16.69	90.64905497	\	\	\
875	17.05	90.93928674	\	\	\
876	17.29	91.13277458	\	\	\
877	17.33	91.16502256	\	\	\
878	17.36	91.18920854	\	\	\
879	17.34	91.17308455	\	\	\
880	17.21	91.06827864	\	\	\
881	17.21	91.06827864	\	\	\

TABLE 4 Historical inundation data used for the flooding model. (*cont.*)

Year	Maximum at Roda	Recalculated Maximum at Aswan Based on Roda	Known Maximum Aswan	Average 10 Day Minima Aswan	Average 10 Day Maxima Aswan
882	17.25	91.10052661	\	\	\
883	17.33	91.16502256	\	\	\
884	16.44	90.44750514	\	\	\
885	16.75	90.69742693	\	\	\
886	16.59	90.56843504	\	\	\
887	16.15	90.21370732	\	\	\
888	16.18	90.2378933	\	\	\
889	17.21	91.06827864	\	\	\
890	17.29	91.13277458	\	\	\
891	17.29	91.13277458	\	\	\
892	17.25	91.10052661	\	\	\
893	17.13	91.00378269	\	\	\
894	16.02	90.10890141	\	\	\
895	15.97	90.06859144	\	\	\
896	16.85	90.77804687	\	\	\
897	16.39	90.40719517	\	\	\
898	16.85	90.77804687	\	\	\
899	17.09	90.97153471	\	\	\
900	17.13	91.00378269	\	\	\
901	16.56	90.54424906	\	\	\
902	17.25	91.10052661	\	\	\
903	16.51	90.50393909	\	\	\
904	15.17	89.42363196	\	\	\
905	16.51	90.50393909	\	\	\
906	16.6	90.57649703	\	\	\
907	16.23	90.27820327	\	\	\

TABLE 4 Historical inundation data used for the flooding model. (*cont.*)

Year	Maximum at Roda	Recalculated Maximum at Aswan Based on Roda	Known Maximum Aswan	Average 10 Day Minima Aswan	Average 10 Day Maxima Aswan
908	16.33	90.35882321	\	\	\
909	17.31	91.14889857	\	\	\
910	17.15	91.01990667	\	\	\
911	17.09	90.97153471	\	\	\
912	17.09	90.97153471	\	\	\
913	17.42	91.2375805	\	\	\
914	17.42	91.2375805	\	\	\
915	16.69	90.64905497	\	\	\
916	16.37	90.39107118	\	\	\
917	16.37	90.39107118	\	\	\
918	16.52	90.51200108	\	\	\
919	17.31	91.14889857	\	\	\
920	17.13	91.00378269	\	\	\
921	17	90.89897677	\	\	\
922	17.11	90.9876587	\	\	\
923	16.73	90.68130295	\	\	\
924	17.4	91.22145651	\	\	\
925	17.04	90.93122475	\	\	\
926	17.04	90.93122475	\	\	\
927	15.88	89.9960335	\	\	\
928	17.4	91.22145651	\	\	\
929	17.38	91.20533252	\	\	\
930	16.98	90.88285278	\	\	\
931	16.1	90.17339736	\	\	\
932	17.19	91.05215465	\	\	\
933	16.48	90.47975311	\	\	\

TABLE 4 Historical inundation data used for the flooding model. (*cont.*)

Year	Maximum at Roda	Recalculated Maximum at Aswan Based on Roda	Known Maximum Aswan	Average 10 Day Minima Aswan	Average 10 Day Maxima Aswan
934	17.21	91.06827864	\	\	\
935	16.81	90.7457989	\	\	\
936	16.87	90.79417086	\	\	\
937	16.79	90.72967491	\	\	\
938	17.13	91.00378269	\	\	\
939	15.95	90.05246745	\	\	\
940	16.6	90.57649703	\	\	\
941	16.27	90.31045125	\	\	\
942	16.17	90.22983131	\	\	\
943	17.86	91.59230821	\	\	\
944	16.65	90.616807	\	\	\
945	16.25	90.29432726	\	\	\
946	16.14	90.20564533	\	\	\
947	16.17	90.22983131	\	\	\
948	15.88	89.9960335	\	\	\
949	16.25	90.29432726	\	\	\
950	17.29	91.13277458	\	\	\
951	16.61	90.58455903	\	\	\
952	16.67	90.63293099	\	\	\
953	17.4	91.22145651	\	\	\
954	16.61	90.58455903	\	\	\
955	17.06	90.94734873	\	\	\
956	16.61	90.58455903	\	\	\
957	16.85	90.77804687	\	\	\
958	17.33	91.16502256	\	\	\
959	17.33	91.16502256	\	\	\

TABLE 4 Historical inundation data used for the flooding model. (*cont.*)

Year	Maximum at Roda	Recalculated Maximum at Aswan Based on Roda	Known Maximum Aswan	Average 10 Day Minima Aswan	Average 10 Day Maxima Aswan
960	16.94	90.85060481	\	\	\
961	17.4	91.22145651	\	\	\
962	16.61	90.58455903	\	\	\
963	16.33	90.35882321	\	\	\
964	16.1	90.17339736	\	\	\
965	16.77	90.71355092	\	\	\
966	15.92	90.02828147	\	\	\
967	14.96	89.2543301	\	\	\
968	17.21	91.06827864	\	\	\
969	17.11	90.9876587	\	\	\
970	17.31	91.14889857	\	\	\
971	17.34	91.17308455	\	\	\
972	17.02	90.91510076	\	\	\
973	16.98	90.88285278	\	\	\
974	16.75	90.69742693	\	\	\
975	16.87	90.79417086	\	\	\
976	16.92	90.83448082	\	\	\
977	16.56	90.54424906	\	\	\
978	16.56	90.54424906	\	\	\
979	16.96	90.8667288	\	\	\
980	16.94	90.85060481	\	\	\
981	16.1	90.17339736	\	\	\
982	16.06	90.14114938	\	\	\
983	17.02	90.91510076	\	\	\
984	16.52	90.51200108	\	\	\
985	16.56	90.54424906	\	\	\

TABLE 4 Historical inundation data used for the flooding model. (*cont.*)

Year	Maximum at Roda	Recalculated Maximum at Aswan Based on Roda	Known Maximum Aswan	Average 10 Day Minima Aswan	Average 10 Day Maxima Aswan
986	17.34	91.17308455	\	\	\
987	17.13	91.00378269	\	\	\
988	17.17	91.03603066	\	\	\
989	16.39	90.40719517	\	\	\
990	16.87	90.79417086	\	\	\
991	16.92	90.83448082	\	\	\
992	16.83	90.76192288	\	\	\
993	17.34	91.17308455	\	\	\
994	16.61	90.58455903	\	\	\
995	16.61	90.58455903	\	\	\
996	16.46	90.46362912	\	\	\
997	16.61	90.58455903	\	\	\
998	16.61	90.58455903	\	\	\
999	16.87	90.79417086	\	\	\
1000	16.52	90.51200108	\	\	\
1001	16.87	90.79417086	\	\	\
1002	17.13	91.00378269	\	\	\
1003	16.77	90.71355092	\	\	\
1004	17.23	91.08440262	\	\	\
1005	16.54	90.52812507	\	\	\
1006	16.79	90.72967491	\	\	\
1007	15.86	89.97990951	\	\	\
1008	15.72	89.8670416	\	\	\
1009	16.92	90.83448082	\	\	\
1010	16.92	90.83448082	\	\	\
1011	16.83	90.76192288	\	\	\

TABLE 4 Historical inundation data used for the flooding model. (*cont.*)

Year	Maximum at Roda	Recalculated Maximum at Aswan Based on Roda	Known Maximum Aswan	Average 10 Day Minima Aswan	Average 10 Day Maxima Aswan
1012	16.67	90.63293099	\	\	\
1013	17.17	91.03603066	\	\	\
1014	16.48	90.47975311	\	\	\
1015	16.52	90.51200108	\	\	\
1016	17.02	90.91510076	\	\	\
1017	16.79	90.72967491	\	\	\
1018	16.92	90.83448082	\	\	\
1019	18.01	91.71323812	\	\	\
1020	17	90.89897677	\	\	\
1021	16.54	90.52812507	\	\	\
1022	16.83	90.76192288	\	\	\
1023	15.82	89.94766154	\	\	\
1024	16.48	90.47975311	\	\	\
1025	16.56	90.54424906	\	\	\
1026	16.61	90.58455903	\	\	\
1027	16.73	90.68130295	\	\	\
1028	17.02	90.91510076	\	\	\
1029	16.48	90.47975311	\	\	\
1030	16.6	90.57649703	\	\	\
1031	17.06	90.94734873	\	\	\
1032	16.56	90.54424906	\	\	\
1033	16.52	90.51200108	\	\	\
1034	16.88	90.80223285	\	\	\
1035	16.77	90.71355092	\	\	\
1036	16.77	90.71355092	\	\	\
1037	16.19	90.2459553	\	\	\

TABLE 4 Historical inundation data used for the flooding model. (cont.)

Year	Maximum at Roda	Recalculated Maximum at Aswan Based on Roda	Known Maximum Aswan	Average 10 Day Minima Aswan	Average 10 Day Maxima Aswan
1038	16.41	90.42331915	\	\	\
1039	17.33	91.16502256	\	\	\
1040	17.13	91.00378269	\	\	\
1041	17.33	91.16502256	\	\	\
1042	17.27	91.1166506	\	\	\
1043	17.25	91.10052661	\	\	\
1044	17.52	91.31820043	\	\	\
1045	17.33	91.16502256	\	\	\
1046	17.33	91.16502256	\	\	\
1047	17.31	91.14889857	\	\	\
1048	17.27	91.1166506	\	\	\
1049	17.11	90.9876587	\	\	\
1050	17.25	91.10052661	\	\	\
1051	17.17	91.03603066	\	\	\
1052	17.04	90.93122475	\	\	\
1053	16.94	90.85060481	\	\	\
1054	17.02	90.91510076	\	\	\
1055	16.56	90.54424906	\	\	\
1056	17.19	91.05215465	\	\	\
1057	17	90.89897677	\	\	\
1058	16.71	90.66517896	\	\	\
1059	16.46	90.46362912	\	\	\
1060	16.65	90.616807	\	\	\
1061	16.83	90.76192288	\	\	\
1062	16.94	90.85060481	\	\	\
1063	17.17	91.03603066	\	\	\

TABLE 4 Historical inundation data used for the flooding model. (*cont.*)

Year	Maximum at Roda	Recalculated Maximum at Aswan Based on Roda	Known Maximum Aswan	Average 10 Day Minima Aswan	Average 10 Day Maxima Aswan
1064	16.54	90.52812507	\	\	\
1065	16.67	90.63293099	\	\	\
1066	16.81	90.7457989	\	\	\
1067	16.81	90.7457989	\	\	\
1068	16.14	90.20564533	\	\	\
1069	17.29	91.13277458	\	\	\
1070	16.48	90.47975311	\	\	\
1071	17	90.89897677	\	\	\
1072	16.67	90.63293099	\	\	\
1073	16.61	90.58455903	\	\	\
1074	16.54	90.52812507	\	\	\
1075	17.07	90.95541073	\	\	\
1076	16.75	90.69742693	\	\	\
1077	17.19	91.05215465	\	\	\
1078	17.13	91.00378269	\	\	\
1079	17.33	91.16502256	\	\	\
1080	16.77	90.71355092	\	\	\
1081	17.65	91.42300635	\	\	\
1082	16.21	90.26207928	\	\	\
1083	17.11	90.9876587	\	\	\
1084	17.19	91.05215465	\	\	\
1085	16.12	90.18952134	\	\	\
1086	17.23	91.08440262	\	\	\
1087	17.07	90.95541073	\	\	\
1088	17.48	91.28595246	\	\	\
1089	16.65	90.616807	\	\	\

TABLE 4 Historical inundation data used for the flooding model. (*cont.*)

Year	Maximum at Roda	Recalculated Maximum at Aswan Based on Roda	Known Maximum Aswan	Average 10 Day Minima Aswan	Average 10 Day Maxima Aswan
1090	17.4	91.22145651	\	\	\
1091	16.9	90.81835684	\	\	\
1092	16.69	90.64905497	\	\	\
1093	16.54	90.52812507	\	\	\
1094	16.92	90.83448082	\	\	\
1095	17.17	91.03603066	\	\	\
1096	17.73	91.4875023	\	\	\
1097	16.96	90.8667288	\	\	\
1098	17.52	91.31820043	\	\	\
1099	16.75	90.69742693	\	\	\
1100	17.69	91.45525432	\	\	\
1101	17.53	91.32626243	\	\	\
1102	17.19	91.05215465	\	\	\
1103	16.96	90.8667288	\	\	\
1104	17.19	91.05215465	\	\	\
1105	16.71	90.66517896	\	\	\
1106	16.71	90.66517896	\	\	\
1107	17.88	91.6084322	\	\	\
1108	17.29	91.13277458	\	\	\
1109	17.25	91.10052661	\	\	\
1110	17.04	90.93122475	\	\	\
1111	17.02	90.91510076	\	\	\
1112	17.02	90.91510076	\	\	\
1113	17.44	91.25370449	\	\	\
1114	16.94	90.85060481	\	\	\
1115	17.4	91.22145651	\	\	\

TABLE 4 Historical inundation data used for the flooding model. (*cont.*)

Year	Maximum at Roda	Recalculated Maximum at Aswan Based on Roda	Known Maximum Aswan	Average 10 Day Minima Aswan	Average 10 Day Maxima Aswan
1116	17.06	90.94734873	\	\	\
1117	17.31	91.14889857	\	\	\
1118	17.48	91.28595246	\	\	\
1119	17.53	91.32626243	\	\	\
1120	17.42	91.2375805	\	\	\
1121	17.13	91.00378269	\	\	\
1122	17.46	91.26982847	\	\	\
1123	17.59	91.37463439	\	\	\
1124	17.67	91.43913034	\	\	\
1125	17.67	91.43913034	\	\	\
1126	17.42	91.2375805	\	\	\
1127	16.94	90.85060481	\	\	\
1128	17.65	91.42300635	\	\	\
1129	17.5	91.30207645	\	\	\
1130	17.02	90.91510076	\	\	\
1131	16.83	90.76192288	\	\	\
1132	17.13	91.00378269	\	\	\
1133	17.23	91.08440262	\	\	\
1134	17.38	91.20533252	\	\	\
1135	17.46	91.26982847	\	\	\
1136	17.07	90.95541073	\	\	\
1137	17.25	91.10052661	\	\	\
1138	17.63	91.40688236	\	\	\
1139	17.5	91.30207645	\	\	\
1140	16.81	90.7457989	\	\	\
1141	17.17	91.03603066	\	\	\

TABLE 4 Historical inundation data used for the flooding model. (*cont.*)

Year	Maximum at Roda	Recalculated Maximum at Aswan Based on Roda	Known Maximum Aswan	Average 10 Day Minima Aswan	Average 10 Day Maxima Aswan
1142	16.69	90.64905497	\	\	\
1143	17.4	91.22145651	\	\	\
1144	16.65	90.616807	\	\	\
1145	17.48	91.28595246	\	\	\
1146	17.4	91.22145651	\	\	\
1147	16.87	90.79417086	\	\	\
1148	17.65	91.42300635	\	\	\
1149	17.65	91.42300635	\	\	\
1150	17.19	91.05215465	\	\	\
1151	17.48	91.28595246	\	\	\
1152	17.48	91.28595246	\	\	\
1153	17.06	90.94734873	\	\	\
1154	17.33	91.16502256	\	\	\
1155	17.27	91.1166506	\	\	\
1156	17.09	90.97153471	\	\	\
1157	17.61	91.39075838	\	\	\
1158	17.59	91.37463439	\	\	\
1159	16.04	90.1250254	\	\	\
1160	17.59	91.37463439	\	\	\
1161	17.73	91.4875023	\	\	\
1162	17.02	90.91510076	\	\	\
1163	17.09	90.97153471	\	\	\
1164	17.59	91.37463439	\	\	\
1165	17.29	91.13277458	\	\	\
1166	17.38	91.20533252	\	\	\
1167	16.92	90.83448082	\	\	\

TABLE 4 Historical inundation data used for the flooding model. (*cont.*)

Year	Maximum at Roda	Recalculated Maximum at Aswan Based on Roda	Known Maximum Aswan	Average 10 Day Minima Aswan	Average 10 Day Maxima Aswan
1168	17.38	91.20533252	\	\	\
1169	16.71	90.66517896	\	\	\
1170	16.75	90.69742693	\	\	\
1171	16.88	90.80223285	\	\	\
1172	17.33	91.16502256	\	\	\
1173	17.75	91.50362628	\	\	\
1174	17.13	91.00378269	\	\	\
1175	17.31	91.14889857	\	\	\
1176	16.67	90.63293099	\	\	\
1177	16.88	90.80223285	\	\	\
1178	17.34	91.17308455	\	\	\
1179	16.85	90.77804687	\	\	\
1180	17.53	91.32626243	\	\	\
1181	16.79	90.72967491	\	\	\
1182	17.5	91.30207645	\	\	\
1183	17.38	91.20533252	\	\	\
1184	17.65	91.42300635	\	\	\
1185	16.96	90.8667288	\	\	\
1186	16.96	90.8667288	\	\	\
1187	17.17	91.03603066	\	\	\
1188	17.19	91.05215465	\	\	\
1189	17.36	91.18920854	\	\	\
1190	17.48	91.28595246	\	\	\
1191	17.67	91.43913034	\	\	\
1192	17.15	91.01990667	\	\	\
1193	17.55	91.34238641	\	\	\

TABLE 4 Historical inundation data used for the flooding model. (*cont.*)

Year	Maximum at Roda	Recalculated Maximum at Aswan Based on Roda	Known Maximum Aswan	Average 10 Day Minima Aswan	Average 10 Day Maxima Aswan
1194	16.9	90.81835684	\	\	\
1195	17.13	91.00378269	\	\	\
1196	17.29	91.13277458	\	\	\
1197	17.34	91.17308455	\	\	\
1198	17.44	91.25370449	\	\	\
1199	17.25	91.10052661	\	\	\
1200	15.03	89.31076405	\	\	\
1201	16.33	90.35882321	\	\	\
1202	16.46	90.46362912	\	\	\
1203	16.94	90.85060481	\	\	\
1204	17.34	91.17308455	\	\	\
1205	17.55	91.34238641	\	\	\
1206	17.25	91.10052661	\	\	\
1207	17.02	90.91510076	\	\	\
1208	16.94	90.85060481	\	\	\
1209	16.71	90.66517896	\	\	\
1210	16.79	90.72967491	\	\	\
1211	16.15	90.21370732	\	\	\
1212	16.69	90.64905497	\	\	\
1213	16.96	90.8667288	\	\	\
1214	16.83	90.76192288	\	\	\
1215	16.63	90.60068301	\	\	\
1216	16.92	90.83448082	\	\	\
1217	17.27	91.1166506	\	\	\
1218	16.6	90.57649703	\	\	\
1219	16.94	90.85060481	\	\	\

TABLE 4 Historical inundation data used for the flooding model. (*cont.*)

Year	Maximum at Roda	Recalculated Maximum at Aswan Based on Roda	Known Maximum Aswan	Average 10 Day Minima Aswan	Average 10 Day Maxima Aswan
1220	16.63	90.60068301	\	\	\
1221	16.98	90.88285278	\	\	\
1222	17	90.89897677	\	\	\
1223	16.94	90.85060481	\	\	\
1224	16.92	90.83448082	\	\	\
1225	16.85	90.77804687	\	\	\
1226	17.42	91.2375805	\	\	\
1227	17.17	91.03603066	\	\	\
1229	16.69	90.64905497	\	\	\
1230	16.54	90.52812507	\	\	\
1231	16.48	90.47975311	\	\	\
1232	16.54	90.52812507	\	\	\
1233	17.52	91.31820043	\	\	\
1234	16.54	90.52812507	\	\	\
1235	16.98	90.88285278	\	\	\
1236	16.92	90.83448082	\	\	\
1237	16.94	90.85060481	\	\	\
1238	16.69	90.64905497	\	\	\
1239	16.85	90.77804687	\	\	\
1240	16.65	90.616807	\	\	\
1241	16.88	90.80223285	\	\	\
1242	16.54	90.52812507	\	\	\
1243	17.55	91.34238641	\	\	\
1244	16.02	90.10890141	\	\	\
1245	15.55	89.72998771	\	\	\
1246	17.11	90.9876587	\	\	\

TABLE 4 Historical inundation data used for the flooding model. (*cont.*)

Year	Maximum at Roda	Recalculated Maximum at Aswan Based on Roda	Known Maximum Aswan	Average 10 Day Minima Aswan	Average 10 Day Maxima Aswan
1247	17.31	91.14889857	\	\	\
1248	17.38	91.20533252	\	\	\
1249	17.09	90.97153471	\	\	\
1250	16.98	90.88285278	\	\	\
1251	17.75	91.50362628	\	\	\
1252	17.73	91.4875023	\	\	\
1253	17.27	91.1166506	\	\	\
1254	17.17	91.03603066	\	\	\
1255	17.4	91.22145651	\	\	\
1256	17.46	91.26982847	\	\	\
1257	17.27	91.1166506	\	\	\
1258	17.04	90.93122475	\	\	\
1259	17.42	91.2375805	\	\	\
1260	17.61	91.39075838	\	\	\
1261	17.19	91.05215465	\	\	\
1262	17.4	91.22145651	\	\	\
1263	17.19	91.05215465	\	\	\
1264	17.17	91.03603066	\	\	\
1265	16.75	90.69742693	\	\	\
1266	17.63	91.40688236	\	\	\
1267	16.75	90.69742693	\	\	\
1268	17.4	91.22145651	\	\	\
1269	17.07	90.95541073	\	\	\
1270	17.36	91.18920854	\	\	\
1271	16.71	90.66517896	\	\	\
1272	17.61	91.39075838	\	\	\

TABLE 4 Historical inundation data used for the flooding model. (*cont.*)

Year	Maximum at Roda	Recalculated Maximum at Aswan Based on Roda	Known Maximum Aswan	Average 10 Day Minima Aswan	Average 10 Day Maxima Aswan
1273	17.19	91.05215465	\	\	\
1274	17.06	90.94734873	\	\	\
1275	17	90.89897677	\	\	\
1276	17.61	91.39075838	\	\	\
1277	17.55	91.34238641	\	\	\
1278	17.5	91.30207645	\	\	\
1279	17.42	91.2375805	\	\	\
1280	17.84	91.57618423	\	\	\
1281	17.48	91.28595246	\	\	\
1282	17.29	91.13277458	\	\	\
1283	17.09	90.97153471	\	\	\
1284	17	90.89897677	\	\	\
1285	16.87	90.79417086	\	\	\
1286	17.02	90.91510076	\	\	\
1287	17.13	91.00378269	\	\	\
1288	17.48	91.28595246	\	\	\
1289	17.13	91.00378269	\	\	\
1290	16.35	90.37494719	\	\	\
1291	17.07	90.95541073	\	\	\
1292	16.94	90.85060481	\	\	\
1293	17.17	91.03603066	\	\	\
1294	16.15	90.21370732	\	\	\
1295	16.81	90.7457989	\	\	\
1296	17.42	91.2375805	\	\	\
1297	16.37	90.39107118	\	\	\
1298	17.13	91.00378269	\	\	\

TABLE 4 Historical inundation data used for the flooding model. (*cont.*)

Year	Maximum at Roda	Recalculated Maximum at Aswan Based on Roda	Known Maximum Aswan	Average 10 Day Minima Aswan	Average 10 Day Maxima Aswan
1299	17.25	91.10052661	\	\	\
1300	16.6	90.57649703	\	\	\
1301	16.83	90.76192288	\	\	\
1302	16.73	90.68130295	\	\	\
1303	17.4	91.22145651	\	\	\
1304	16.79	90.72967491	\	\	\
1305	16.71	90.66517896	\	\	\
1306	16.77	90.71355092	\	\	\
1307	17.07	90.95541073	\	\	\
1308	17.42	91.2375805	\	\	\
1309	16.52	90.51200108	\	\	\
1310	17.46	91.26982847	\	\	\
1311	16.88	90.80223285	\	\	\
1312	16.9	90.81835684	\	\	\
1313	16.61	90.58455903	\	\	\
1314	16.81	90.7457989	\	\	\
1315	17.27	91.1166506	\	\	\
1316	17.36	91.18920854	\	\	\
1317	17.4	91.22145651	\	\	\
1318	16.81	90.7457989	\	\	\
1319	17.15	91.01990667	\	\	\
1320	16.9	90.81835684	\	\	\
1321	16.58	90.56037304	\	\	\
1322	16.88	90.80223285	\	\	\
1323	17.52	91.31820043	\	\	\
1324	17.77	91.51975027	\	\	\

TABLE 4 Historical inundation data used for the flooding model. (*cont.*)

Year	Maximum at Roda	Recalculated Maximum at Aswan Based on Roda	Known Maximum Aswan	Average 10 Day Minima Aswan	Average 10 Day Maxima Aswan
1325	16.88	90.80223285	\	\	\
1326	16.85	90.77804687	\	\	\
1327	17.04	90.93122475	\	\	\
1328	17.57	91.3585104	\	\	\
1329	16.58	90.56037304	\	\	\
1330	17.13	91.00378269	\	\	\
1331	16.9	90.81835684	\	\	\
1332	17.61	91.39075838	\	\	\
1333	17.25	91.10052661	\	\	\
1334	16.9	90.81835684	\	\	\
1335	17.61	91.39075838	\	\	\
1336	17.25	91.10052661	\	\	\
1337	16.87	90.79417086	\	\	\
1338	16.67	90.63293099	\	\	\
1339	17.09	90.97153471	\	\	\
1340	16.85	90.77804687	\	\	\
1341	17.57	91.3585104	\	\	\
1342	16.94	90.85060481	\	\	\
1343	17.73	91.4875023	\	\	\
1344	17.73	91.4875023	\	\	\
1345	17.69	91.45525432	\	\	\
1346	17.04	90.93122475	\	\	\
1347	17.09	90.97153471	\	\	\
1348	16.92	90.83448082	\	\	\
1349	17.38	91.20533252	\	\	\
1350	16.94	90.85060481	\	\	\

TABLE 4 Historical inundation data used for the flooding model. (*cont.*)

Year	Maximum at Roda	Recalculated Maximum at Aswan Based on Roda	Known Maximum Aswan	Average 10 Day Minima Aswan	Average 10 Day Maxima Aswan
1351	16.96	90.8667288	\	\	\
1352	17.71	91.47137831	\	\	\
1353	17.71	91.47137831	\	\	\
1354	17.86	91.59230821	\	\	\
1355	17.8	91.54393625	\	\	\
1356	17.33	91.16502256	\	\	\
1357	17.52	91.31820043	\	\	\
1358	16.94	90.85060481	\	\	\
1359	17.92	91.64068017	\	\	\
1360	20.17	93.45462871	\	\	\
1361	17.59	91.37463439	\	\	\
1362	16.98	90.88285278	\	\	\
1363	17.02	90.91510076	\	\	\
1364	17.17	91.03603066	\	\	\
1365	17.25	91.10052661	\	\	\
1366	17.25	91.10052661	\	\	\
1367	17.98	91.68905214	\	\	\
1368	17.4	91.22145651	\	\	\
1369	16.94	90.85060481	\	\	\
1370	16.83	90.76192288	\	\	\
1371	17.02	90.91510076	\	\	\
1372	17.48	91.28595246	\	\	\
1373	16.39	90.40719517	\	\	\
1374	17.04	90.93122475	\	\	\
1375	17.19	91.05215465	\	\	\
1376	17.9	91.62455619	\	\	\

TABLE 4 Historical inundation data used for the flooding model. (*cont.*)

Year	Maximum at Roda	Recalculated Maximum at Aswan Based on Roda	Known Maximum Aswan	Average 10 Day Minima Aswan	Average 10 Day Maxima Aswan
1377	17.63	91.40688236	\	\	\
1378	17.96	91.67292815	\	\	\
1379	17.9	91.62455619	\	\	\
1380	17.02	90.91510076	\	\	\
1381	18.09	91.77773406	\	\	\
1382	18.44	92.05990384	\	\	\
1383	18.13	91.80998204	\	\	\
1384	18.01	91.71323812	\	\	\
1385	17.23	91.08440262	\	\	\
1386	18.38	92.01153188	\	\	\
1387	17.69	91.45525432	\	\	\
1388	17.94	91.65680416	\	\	\
1389	17.94	91.65680416	\	\	\
1390	17.44	91.25370449	\	\	\
1391	17.88	91.6084322	\	\	\
1392	18.09	91.77773406	\	\	\
1393	17.33	91.16502256	\	\	\
1394	17.15	91.01990667	\	\	\
1395	17.09	90.97153471	\	\	\
1396	17.9	91.62455619	\	\	\
1397	18.09	91.77773406	\	\	\
1398	17.99	91.69711413	\	\	\
1399	17.5	91.30207645	\	\	\
1400	17.67	91.43913034	\	\	\
1401	17.34	91.17308455	\	\	\
1402	17.4	91.22145651	\	\	\

TABLE 4 Historical inundation data used for the flooding model. (*cont.*)

Year	Maximum at Roda	Recalculated Maximum at Aswan Based on Roda	Known Maximum Aswan	Average 10 Day Minima Aswan	Average 10 Day Maxima Aswan
1403	16.73	90.68130295	\	\	\
1404	17.92	91.64068017	\	\	\
1405	17.84	91.57618423	\	\	\
1406	18.09	91.77773406	\	\	\
1407	18.05	91.74548609	\	\	\
1408	16.96	90.8667288	\	\	\
1409	18.38	92.01153188	\	\	\
1410	18.26	91.91478795	\	\	\
1411	17.79	91.53587426	\	\	\
1412	17.75	91.50362628	\	\	\
1413	18.25	91.90672596	\	\	\
1414	17.96	91.67292815	\	\	\
1415	18.38	92.01153188	\	\	\
1416	18.38	92.01153188	\	\	\
1417	18.01	91.71323812	\	\	\
1418	17.59	91.37463439	\	\	\
1419	17.67	91.43913034	\	\	\
1420	17.46	91.26982847	\	\	\
1421	17.88	91.6084322	\	\	\
1422	18.61	92.19695773	\	\	\
1423	17.84	91.57618423	\	\	\
1424	17.21	91.06827864	\	\	\
1425	18.38	92.01153188	\	\	\
1426	18.38	92.01153188	\	\	\
1427	18.38	92.01153188	\	\	\
1428	18.38	92.01153188	\	\	\

TABLE 4 Historical inundation data used for the flooding model. (*cont.*)

Year	Maximum at Roda	Recalculated Maximum at Aswan Based on Roda	Known Maximum Aswan	Average 10 Day Minima Aswan	Average 10 Day Maxima Aswan
1429	18.17	91.84223001	\	\	\
1430	18.61	92.19695773	\	\	\
1431	18.38	92.01153188	\	\	\
1432	18.48	92.09215181	\	\	\
1433	18.63	92.21308171	\	\	\
1434	18.73	92.29370165	\	\	\
1435	18.61	92.19695773	\	\	\
1436	17.98	91.68905214	\	\	\
1437	18.67	92.24532969	\	\	\
1438	17.79	91.53587426	\	\	\
1439	18.59	92.18083374	\	\	\
1440	18.78	92.33401162	\	\	\
1441	18.67	92.24532969	\	\	\
1442	18.78	92.33401162	\	\	\
1443	18.3	91.94703593	\	\	\
1444	17.67	91.43913034	\	\	\
1445	18.03	91.7293621	\	\	\
1446	18.25	91.90672596	\	\	\
1447	18.13	91.80998204	\	\	\
1448	17.84	91.57618423	\	\	\
1449	17.46	91.26982847	\	\	\
1450	16.15	90.21370732	\	\	\
1451	17.55	91.34238641	\	\	\
1452	18.09	91.77773406	\	\	\
1453	17.82	91.56006024	\	\	\
1454	18.07	91.76161008	\	\	\

TABLE 4 Historical inundation data used for the flooding model. (*cont.*)

Year	Maximum at Roda	Recalculated Maximum at Aswan Based on Roda	Known Maximum Aswan	Average 10 Day Minima Aswan	Average 10 Day Maxima Aswan
1455	18.13	91.80998204	\	\	\
1456	18.09	91.77773406	\	\	\
1457	17.71	91.47137831	\	\	\
1458	17.71	91.47137831	\	\	\
1459	17.88	91.6084322	\	\	\
1460	18.15	91.82610602	\	\	\
1461	17.34	91.17308455	\	\	\
1462	17.52	91.31820043	\	\	\
1463	17.99	91.69711413	\	\	\
1464	18.11	91.79385805	\	\	\
1465	17.86	91.59230821	\	\	\
1466	17.52	91.31820043	\	\	\
1467	17.94	91.65680416	\	\	\
1468	17.63	91.40688236	\	\	\
1469	18.01	91.71323812	\	\	\
1474	16.71	90.66517896	\	\	\
1478	18.78	92.33401162	\	\	\
1484	17.36	91.18920854	\	\	\
1486	17.8	91.54393625	\	\	\
1490	17.11	90.9876587	\	\	\
1492	17.27	91.1166506	\	\	\
1497	16.48	90.47975311	\	\	\
1501	18.19	91.858354	\	\	\
1502	17.96	91.67292815	\	\	\
1503	17.61	91.39075838	\	\	\
1504	17.65	91.42300635	\	\	\

TABLE 4 Historical inundation data used for the flooding model. (*cont.*)

Year	Maximum at Roda	Recalculated Maximum at Aswan Based on Roda	Known Maximum Aswan	Average 10 Day Minima Aswan	Average 10 Day Maxima Aswan
1506	17.9	91.62455619	\	\	\
1507	17.75	91.50362628	\	\	\
1508	17.96	91.67292815	\	\	\
1509	17.82	91.56006024	\	\	\
1510	17.34	91.17308455	\	\	\
1511	18.03	91.7293621	\	\	\
1512	18.59	92.18083374	\	\	\
1513	18.15	91.82610602	\	\	\
1514	18.69	92.26145367	\	\	\
1515	18.09	91.77773406	\	\	\
1516	18.38	92.01153188	\	\	\
1517	17.67	91.43913034	\	\	\
1518	17.52	91.31820043	\	\	\
1519	18.01	91.71323812	\	\	\
1520	17.5	91.30207645	\	\	\
1521	18.3	91.94703593	\	\	\
1522	17.8	91.54393625	\	\	\
1573	18.95	92.47106551	\	\	\
1583	18.95	92.47106551	\	\	\
1587	19.52	92.93059914	\	\	\
1588	18.95	92.47106551	\	\	\
1589	18.28	91.93091194	\	\	\
1590	18.82	92.36625959	\	\	\
1593	18.67	92.24532969	\	\	\
1594	20.17	93.45462871	\	\	\
1595	18.86	92.39850756	\	\	\

TABLE 4 Historical inundation data used for the flooding model. (*cont.*)

Year	Maximum at Roda	Recalculated Maximum at Aswan Based on Roda	Known Maximum Aswan	Average 10 Day Minima Aswan	Average 10 Day Maxima Aswan
1596	19.82	93.17245894	\	\	\
1597	18.91	92.43881753	\	\	\
1600	18.89	92.42269354	\	\	\
1601	17.99	91.69711413	\	\	\
1602	18.19	91.858354	\	\	\
1603	20.11	93.40625675	\	\	\
1604	18.52	92.12439978	\	\	\
1605	19.31	92.76129727	\	\	\
1606	17.89	91.61649419	\	\	\
1607	18.94	92.46300351	\	\	\
1608	19.27	92.7290493	\	\	\
1609	19.42	92.8499792	\	\	\
1610	18.5	92.1082758	\	\	\
1611	20.03	93.3417608	\	\	\
1612	20.03	93.3417608	\	\	\
1613	18.67	92.24532969	\	\	\
1614	19.42	92.8499792	\	\	\
1615	19.3	92.75323528	\	\	\
1616	18.46	92.07602782	\	\	\
1617	18.2	91.86641599	\	\	\
1621	17.86	91.59230821	\	\	\
1622	19.42	92.8499792	\	\	\
1623	20.03	93.3417608	\	\	\
1625	20.03	93.3417608	\	\	\
1635	18.23	91.89060197	\	\	\
1641	16.79	90.72967491	\	\	\

TABLE 4 Historical inundation data used for the flooding model. (*cont.*)

Year	Maximum at Roda	Recalculated Maximum at Aswan Based on Roda	Known Maximum Aswan	Average 10 Day Minima Aswan	Average 10 Day Maxima Aswan
1645	19.67	93.05152904	\	\	\
1650	17.15	91.01990667	\	\	\
1658	19.55	92.95478512	\	\	\
1670	19.31	92.76129727	\	\	\
1688	19.31	92.76129727	\	\	\
1690	19.31	92.76129727	\	\	\
1698	20.03	93.3417608	\	\	\
1701	19.58	92.9789711	\	\	\
1702	19.73	93.099901	\	\	\
1703	18.58	92.17277175	\	\	\
1704	18.89	92.42269354	\	\	\
1707	19.49	92.90641315	\	\	\
1708	18.89	92.42269354	\	\	\
1709	18.58	92.17277175	\	\	\
1710	19.31	92.76129727	\	\	\
1713	18.2	91.86641599	\	\	\
1716	17.15	91.01990667	\	\	\
1720	18.35	91.98734589	\	\	\
1721	19.3	92.75323528	\	\	\
1722	19.64	93.02734306	\	\	\
1723	18.89	92.42269354	\	\	\
1724	19.67	93.05152904	\	\	\
1725	18.53	92.13246178	\	\	\
1726	19.46	92.88222717	\	\	\
1727	19.93	93.26114087	\	\	\
1728	19.45	92.87416518	\	\	\

TABLE 4 Historical inundation data used for the flooding model. (*cont.*)

Year	Maximum at Roda	Recalculated Maximum at Aswan Based on Roda	Known Maximum Aswan	Average 10 Day Minima Aswan	Average 10 Day Maxima Aswan
1729	19.67	93.05152904	\	\	\
1731	18.8	92.3501356	\	\	\
1732	19.79	93.14827296	\	\	\
1733	19.36	92.80160724	\	\	\
1734	19.09	92.58393341	\	\	\
1735	19.51	92.92253714	\	\	\
1736	20.09	93.39013276	\	\	\
1737	18.86	92.39850756	\	\	\
1738	20.21	93.48687669	\	\	\
1739	19.85	93.19664492	\	\	\
1740	20.12	93.41431875	\	\	\
1741	19.79	93.14827296	\	\	\
1742	19.85	93.19664492	\	\	\
1743	19.49	92.90641315	\	\	\
1744	19.67	93.05152904	\	\	\
1745	20.03	93.3417608	\	\	\
1746	19.96	93.28532685	\	\	\
1747	20.08	93.38207077	\	\	\
1748	19.4	92.83385521	\	\	\
1749	19.28	92.73711129	\	\	\
1750	19.33	92.77742126	\	\	\
1751	20.03	93.3417608	\	\	\
1752	18.79	92.34207361	\	\	\
1753	18.85	92.39044557	\	\	\
1754	19.57	92.9709091	\	\	\
1755	19.78	93.14021097	\	\	\

TABLE 4 Historical inundation data used for the flooding model. (*cont.*)

Year	Maximum at Roda	Recalculated Maximum at Aswan Based on Roda	Known Maximum Aswan	Average 10 Day Minima Aswan	Average 10 Day Maxima Aswan
1756	19.57	92.9709091	\	\	\
1757	20.21	93.48687669	\	\	\
1758	19.49	92.90641315	\	\	\
1759	19.24	92.70486332	\	\	\
1760	20.05	93.35788479	\	\	\
1761	19.39	92.82579322	\	\	\
1762	19.15	92.63230538	\	\	\
1763	20.09	93.39013276	\	\	\
1764	19.76	93.12408698	\	\	\
1765	18.5	92.1082758	\	\	\
1766	18.13	91.80998204	\	\	\
1767	19.79	93.14827296	\	\	\
1768	20.05	93.35788479	\	\	\
1769	19.36	92.80160724	\	\	\
1770	19.91	93.24501688	\	\	\
1771	19.94	93.26920286	\	\	\
1772	18.47	92.08408982	\	\	\
1773	19.04	92.54362345	\	\	\
1774	19.4	92.83385521	\	\	\
1775	19.85	93.19664492	\	\	\
1776	18.68	92.25339168	\	\	\
1777	19.49	92.90641315	\	\	\
1778	19.76	93.12408698	\	\	\
1779	20.03	93.3417608	\	\	\
1780	19.85	93.19664492	\	\	\
1781	19.4	92.83385521	\	\	\

TABLE 4 Historical inundation data used for the flooding model. (*cont.*)

Year	Maximum at Roda	Recalculated Maximum at Aswan Based on Roda	Known Maximum Aswan	Average 10 Day Minima Aswan	Average 10 Day Maxima Aswan
1782	17.96	91.67292815	\	\	\
1783	17.9	91.62455619	\	\	\
1784	18.07	91.76161008	\	\	\
1785	18.59	92.18083374	\	\	\
1786	19.34	92.78548325	\	\	\
1787	19.57	92.9709091	\	\	\
1788	19.49	92.90641315	\	\	\
1789	19.34	92.78548325	\	\	\
1790	19.22	92.68873933	\	\	\
1791	18.44	92.05990384	\	\	\
1792	18.59	92.18083374	\	\	\
1793	18.41	92.03571786	\	\	\
1794	18.37	92.00346988	\	\	\
1795	18.91	92.43881753	\	\	\
1796	18.77	92.32594962	\	\	\
1797	18.83	92.37432158	\	\	\
1798	19.66	93.04346704	\	\	\
1799	19.04	92.54362345	\	\	\
1800	19.94	93.26920286	\	\	\
1813	19.31	92.76129727	\	\	\
1826	18.29	91.93897393	\	\	\
1827	19.58	92.9789711	\	\	\
1828	19.16	92.64036737	\	\	\
1829	20.06	93.36594678	\	\	\
1830	19.07	92.56780943	\	\	\
1831	19.48	92.89835116	\	\	\

TABLE 4 Historical inundation data used for the flooding model. (*cont.*)

Year	Maximum at Roda	Recalculated Maximum at Aswan Based on Roda	Known Maximum Aswan	Average 10 Day Minima Aswan	Average 10 Day Maxima Aswan
1832	19.3	92.75323528	\	\	\
1833	18.22	91.88253998	\	\	\
1834	19.69	93.06765302	\	\	\
1835	18.46	92.07602782	\	\	\
1836	18.85	92.39044557	\	\	\
1837	18.29	91.93897393	\	\	\
1838	19.13	92.61618139	\	\	\
1839	18.58	92.17277175	\	\	\
1840	19.94	93.26920286	\	\	\
1841	20.03	93.3417608	\	\	\
1842	19.88	93.2208309	\	\	\
1843	19.4	92.83385521	\	\	\
1844	19.36	92.80160724	\	\	\
1845	18.82	92.36625959	\	\	\
1846	20.02	93.33369881	\	\	\
1847	19.66	93.04346704	\	\	\
1848	20.12	93.41431875	\	\	\
1849	20.11	93.40625675	\	\	\
1850	19.25	92.71292531	\	\	\
1851	20.17	93.45462871	\	\	\
1852	19.07	92.56780943	\	\	\
1853	20.17	93.45462871	\	\	\
1854	20.02	93.33369881	\	\	\
1855	18.86	92.39850756	\	\	\
1856	20.15	93.43850473	\	\	\
1857	19.28	92.73711129	\	\	\

TABLE 4 Historical inundation data used for the flooding model. (*cont.*)

Year	Maximum at Roda	Recalculated Maximum at Aswan Based on Roda	Known Maximum Aswan	Average 10 Day Minima Aswan	Average 10 Day Maxima Aswan
1858	19.16	92.64036737	\	\	\
1859	19.06	92.55974743	\	\	\
1860	20.11	93.40625675	\	\	\
1861	20.41	93.64811656	\	\	\
1862	19.51	92.92253714	\	\	\
1863	20.61	93.80935643	\	\	\
1864	18.4	92.02765586	\	\	\
1865	19.49	92.90641315	\	\	\
1866	20.91	94.05121623	\	\	\
1867	19.17	92.64842936	\	\	\
1868	18.31	91.95509792	\	\	\
1869	21.16	94.25276607	\	\	93.38
1870	20.43	93.66424054	\	84.54	93.41
1871	19.85	93.19664492	\	85.06	93.04
1872	20.05	93.35788479	\	84.73	93.15
1873	18.57	92.16470975	92.66	84.68	92.45
1874	21.41	94.45431591	93.97	84.37	93.87
1875	20.14	93.43044273	93.36	84.95	93.23
1876	20.39	93.63199257	93.68	85.18	93.48
1877	17.65	91.42300635	91.4	85.14	91.2
1878	21.28	94.34950999	94.15	84.32	93.96
1879	20.3	93.55943463	93.59	86.94	93.45
1880	18.89	92.42269354	92.82	85.88	92.63
1881	20.07	93.37400878	93.14	85.03	93.06
1882	18.8	92.3501356	93	84.56	92.58
1883	20.07	93.37400878	93.18	85.08	93.07

TABLE 4 Historical inundation data used for the flooding model. (*cont.*)

Year	Maximum at Roda	Recalculated Maximum at Aswan Based on Roda	Known Maximum Aswan	Average 10 Day Minima Aswan	Average 10 Day Maxima Aswan
1884	19.22	92.68873933	92.73	85.46	92.52
1885	19.38	92.81773123	93.05	84.6	92.9
1886	19.13	92.61618139	93.04	85.02	92.87
1887	20.64	93.83354241	93.81	85.02	93.72
1888	18.05	91.74548609	92.08	84.95	91.92
1889	19.44	92.86610319	93.36	84.47	93.18
1890	19.83	93.18052093	93.72	84.44	93.44
1891	19.42	92.8499792	92.84	84.82	92.88
1892	20.64	93.83354241	93.88	84.4	93.78
1893	19.4	92.83385521	92.75	85.39	92.56
1894	20.52	93.73679849	93.7	85.01	93.58
1895	20.01	93.32563682	93.74	85.81	93.59
1896	19.83	93.18052093	\	85.57	93.5
1897	19.11	92.6000574	\	85.63	92.68
1898	19.98	93.30145084	\	84.78	93.44
1899	17.48	91.28595246	\	85.19	91.29
1900	19.29	92.74517328	\	84.53	92.75
1901	19.22	92.68873933	\	84.7	92.69
1902	17.9	91.62455619	\	84.81	91.63
1903	19.24	92.70486332	\	84.58	92.71
1904	18.03	91.7293621	\	85.07	91.73
1905	18.29	91.93897393	\	84.53	91.94
1906	19.15	92.63230538	\	84.77	92.9
1907	17.75	91.50362628	\	85.06	91.51
1908	19.79	93.14827296	\	84.68	93.15
1909	19.85	93.19664492	\	85.28	93.2
1910	19.71	93.08377701	\	85.1	93.09

TABLE 4 Historical inundation data used for the flooding model. (*cont.*)

Year	Maximum at Roda	Recalculated Maximum at Aswan Based on Roda	Known Maximum Aswan	Average 10 Day Minima Aswan	Average 10 Day Maxima Aswan
1911	19.33	92.77742126	\	85.14	92.78
1912	18.49	92.1002138	\	84.6	92.1
1913	16.14	90.20564533	\	84.71	90.21
1914	19.42	92.8499792	\	84.51	92.85
1915	17.58	91.3665724	\	84.57	91.37
1916	20.27	93.53524865	\	84.31	93.54
1917	20.35	93.5997446	\	85.08	93.6
1918	18.45	92.06796583	\	86.26	92.07
1919	18.83	92.37432158	\	84.74	92.38
1920	18.96	92.4791275	\	84.46	92.48
1921	18.81	92.3581976	\	84.22	92.36
1922	19.95	93.27726486	\	83.76	93.28
1923	19.3	92.75323528	\	84.54	92.76
1924	19.6	92.99509508	\	84.73	93
1925	18.35	91.98734589	\	84.63	91.99
1926	18.71	92.27757766	\	84.72	92.28
1927	18.55	92.14858577	\	84.79	92.15
1928	18.92	92.44687952	\	84.48	92.45
1929	19.58	92.9789711	\	84.71	92.98
1930	18.3	91.94703593	\	85.02	91.95
1931	19.02	92.52749946	\	84.43	92.53
1932	19.27	92.7290493	\	84.76	92.73
1933	18.96	92.4791275	\	85.18	92.48
1934	19.95	93.27726486	\	84.95	93.28
1935	19.41	92.84191721	\	85.01	92.85
1936	19.29	92.74517328	\	84.95	92.75
1937	19.27	92.7290493	\	84.5	92.73

TABLE 4 Historical inundation data used for the flooding model. (*cont.*)

Year	Maximum at Roda	Recalculated Maximum at Aswan Based on Roda	Known Maximum Aswan	Average 10 Day Minima Aswan	Average 10 Day Maxima Aswan
1938	20.4	93.64005456	\	84.65	93.64
1939	18.24	91.89866397	\	85.36	91.9
1940	18.1	91.78579606	\	84.65	91.79
1941	17.02	90.91510076	\	84.36	90.92
1942	19.06	92.55974743	\	84.91	92.56
1943	19.85	93.19664492	\	84.93	93.2
1944	18.77	92.32594962	\	85.01	92.33
1945	18.14	91.81804403	\	84.42	91.82
1946	20.82	93.97865829	\	84.46	93.98
1947	19.53	92.93866113	\	86.1	92.94
1948	18.26	91.91478795	\	84.88	91.92
1949	18.42	92.04377985	\	85.2	92.05
1950	19.32	92.76935927	\	85.79	92.77
1951	18.51	92.11633779	\	84.41	92.12
1952	19.17	92.64842936	\	84.55	92.65
1953	19.59	92.98703309	\	84.99	92.99
1954	20.46	93.68842652	\	84.62	93.69
1955	19.23	92.69680132	\	85.49	92.7
1956	19.24	92.70486332	\	85.88	92.71
1957	19.54	92.94672312	\	85.77	92.95
1958	20.74	93.91416234	\	84.89	93.92
		94.45431591			

their figures; nevertheless, it is worth noting that as archaeologists we are reliant on the philological and metrological work of philologists, hydrologists, and regional specialists (Said 1993). Beyond this, the records themselves are somewhat uneven, with far more information missing from periods from the latter half of the 2nd millennium CE when the extant data indicates the water

was rising. On a mathematical level, the regression often overestimated the height of the maximal Nile level in Aswan during years of extremely high floods in Rawda (Seidlmayer 2001:113–114). This is somewhat mitigated by the reality that the Nile inundations were comparatively low during the 6th–15th centuries CE, gradually rising throughout the 16th–19th centuries when information on Nile heights was more sporadically recorded. If anything, the absence of Nile heights from this period likely suggests that Nile heights, as represented within the model, may be unduly low.

Beyond concerns related to the records themselves, any modelling of floodplain inundation within GIS software relies upon the use of contemporary Digital Elevation Models. In our case, LandSAT SRTM and TanDEM-X elevation data show a landscape that has dramatically changed in recent years as development projects north of Aswan have surged. Ventures like New Aswan City have created opportunities for salvage archaeology and greatly transformed large swaths of the Nile Valley north of the First Cataract. To the south, the Aswan High Dam construction has radically altered the landscape of Lower Nubia, eliminating the possibility of flood modelling to the south of Aswan without heavily edited elevation data. In the recent and more distant past, inhabitants of the First Cataract region have deployed a variety of different irrigation regimes that impacted the landscape as well. The basin irrigation of the Islamic period does not necessarily map neatly onto Pharaonic agricultural practices, though various authors have highlighted some parallels (cf. Schenkel 1973:775; Lehner 2000:298–305, 314–318, 327–332). Their immediate geomorphological features often significantly impact local flood patterns, and this simple model cannot account for these attributes. Nonetheless, the model allows for historical inundation levels across a wide time frame to be represented spatially within GIS software, together with artificially high flood levels to simulate flood levels during the *African Humid Period*. Our model of the historical flooding patterns near Aswan was built using Ute Susanne Kaden's Floodplain Inundation Calculator plugin within QGIS (Kaden 2022). After loading in the appropriate digital elevation models, we converted them to Float64 formats, as this is necessary to run the Floodplain Inundation Calculator plugin. Next, we had to reformat the data from the historical records so that we could add a simple comma-delimited CSV file to our GIS.⁸ The values in the file provided

8 Certain specifications of the Floodplain Inundation Calculator complicated our efforts here. We initially hoped to include only the data from 622–1898, but the Floodplain Inundation Calculator was designed to take daily input from water gauges to estimate the probability of a given area being inundated each year rather than this kind of historical data. Because the plugin requires data in multiples of 365, we also included the recalculated values of maximum inundation heights through 1911.

the baseline water level data, while the elevation data from the DEM allowed the plugin to generate a new raster file 'flooding622to1911.tif' that reflects the frequency that a given pixel was inundated based on its elevation. This raster was later styled to reflect a spectrum ranging from areas flooded yearly (seen in Fig. 9, in blue) to those only flooded during exceptionally high floods (Fig. 9, in red). To supplement the model generated by the Floodplain Inundation Calculator plugin, estimated flood levels at a specific height were generated from our Digital Elevation Models by using the raster calculator function to shade all pixels below a particular elevation. These more specific calculations were derived from the archaeological and geophysical data discussed above. More localized geo-archaeological investigations of Predynastic sites and their environmental setting are needed to enlarge the current case studies, ideally incorporating HEC-RAS hydrological modelling to simulate flood overflow in their specific areas (Dalton et al. 2023:571–572). Our modelling suggests that the settlements in the First Cataract Region were, also in historical times, out of reach of all but the most extreme inundations.

FIGURE 9 Inundation model from historical flooding data and archaeological sites in the study area.

5 Discussion and Conclusion

The detailed geo-archaeological data available for the valley of Nag el-Qarmila locates the Predynastic settlement on a Late Pleistocene alluvial deposit (Wild Nile) at an elevation of c. 92.50–93.50 m a.s.l., Two main occupational phases are identified in Area B, both dated to the same Naqada I chronological phase (c. 3800–3500 BCE). In the earliest occupation, the space was divided into an area of food processing, composed of a series of hearths in stratigraphical sequence, one with a pot set into the ground nearby, two mud-lined mortars, and a few pits. Postholes are found in the rest of the space. Although it is impossible to reconstruct any architectural feature, their recovery suggests some sort of perishable structure/s was there or in proximity. In the later occupation, the spatial arrangement within the settlement changed, with a working space and a possible hut or floor of some kind located in an open-air courtyard. It is not clear the reason for this change in the village organization, which has no equivalent in the material culture and cannot be associated with an inundation event, or more than one, at the site. There is no clear evidence of alluvial and/or sandy layers intermingled with the two occupational phases, but we cannot confirm the degree of sedentism based on the available stratigraphical sequence. The early Naqada phase lasted at least 300 years, and the two phases of occupations at Nag el-Qarmila could have lasted long enough to cover the whole period or could have been shorter and with a phase of abandonment in between, which, as previously noted, is not identified in the archaeological record. The perishable nature of the architectural features at the site cannot be considered because that does not necessarily mean they have a short-term life. In environments with a warm climate, such as that of southern Egypt, there is no reason to invest in the construction of more complex architecture unless otherwise wanted. This is a well-known fact in Africa, where traditional domestic architecture follows the same logic.⁹

The drill cores in Nag el-Qarmila show how the valley bottom, deeper than nowadays, was regularly inundated by the Nile flooding and that the aquifer was regularly recharged by the Nile flood and winter rains. De Dapper (in Gatto et al. 2009b) suggested that, by damming the upslope part of the thalweg when the flood started to wane, the local community could have caught part of the flood water to obtain a reservoir. This could have been used to irrigate the downslope part of the thalweg when it was dry again. Those hydraulic conditions would have made agriculture possible during a large part of the

9 See, for instance, the <http://www.africavernaculararchitecture.com/> website, for an overview of traditional domestic architecture in Africa.

year, although it could have only been enough to support a small number of people due to the limited catchment area. However, it must be noted that an island is located right in front of the valley of Nag el-Qarmila, so there may have been more agricultural land available for the community than in the valley proper. As for the reconstructed geomorphology, no evidence of alluvial levels contemporary to the Predynastic settlements was identified in the village area, a fact that would support the idea that the settlement was only occasionally reached by the inundation waters.

Broadly speaking, the pattern of rising Nile floods during the latter half of the 2nd millennium CE is the inverse of the archaeological evidence from Elephantine from about 3100–2300 BCE, with roughly comparable average maximum inundation levels. The raster image generated by the Floodplain Inundation Calculator provides a visual reference to the areas in the modern landscape that would typically have been inundated and those which were only threatened by the highest, most severe floods. Even if the most extreme examples of high floods from later periods were a kind of baseline average for the 4th millennium BCE, cemetery sites like WK14 in Nag el-Qarmila were essentially only threatened by one in ten-thousand-year flooding events. By contrast, the settlement sites WK15 in Nag el-Qarmila and WT27 in Wadi el-Tawil were located beyond the reach of typical inundations from the medieval periods (Figs 10–11), but the higher waters of the Early Dynastic Period or 4th millennium BCE may well have occasionally damaged some of these sites, particularly in places where the valley is narrower than Nag el-Qarmila or Wadi el-Tawil (Figs 12–13). It is plausible that additional settlements were damaged or buried under alluvial silts from such inundations.

The estimated high flood levels of the First Dynasty at Elephantine, 94.50–94.00 m a.s.l., allow us to better understand possible contemporary inundation levels at Nag el-Qarmila. We have established a mean drop of the Nile level of 70mm/km, corresponding to a drop of 1.20 m over the distance of 17 km between Elephantine and Nag el-Qarmila. This means that the high inundation levels of that time at the latter site would have been around 92.80–93.30m a.s.l. Elevations measured at the site place the settlement at an elevation of c. 92.50–93.50 m a.s.l., right at the edge of the highest inundation on record thus far. The lack of information about the inundation levels during the 4th millennium BCE, unfortunately, prevents us from making any further calculations, but the absence of alluvial silts intermingled with occupational layers suggests that the excavated sectors of the Nag el-Qarmila were never or rarely damaged by flooding. This suggests that, contrary to current hypotheses, the average high inundation level for the early 4th millennium was similar to that of the late millennium.

FIGURE 10 Inundation model from historical flooding data and archaeological sites in Nag el-Qarmila.

FIGURE 11 Inundation model from historical flooding data and archaeological sites in Wadi el-Tawil.

FIGURE 12 Inundation model from archaeological flooding data and archaeological sites in Nag el-Qarmila.

FIGURE 13 Inundation model from archaeological flooding data and archaeological sites in Wadi el-Tawil.

In conclusion, we can assert that there seems to have been a conscious effort to construct dwellings in places close to but clearly beyond the floodplain itself. Indeed, the survival of these remains suggests that they were not severely eroded by floods at any point in the subsequent 5500-plus years after their foundation. It is, however, plausible that the extremely high Nile floods of the Early Dynastic Period (1st–2nd Dynasties/3100–2650 BCE) may have damaged some settlements and buried them beneath alluvial silt. However, AKAPs survey efforts suggest that these sites seem to have been deliberately situated to allow for more permanent occupation rather than maximizing proximity to riverine or wadi resources. Given the placement of these settlements, the annual flooding of the Nile cannot be considered a major argument in favor of a seasonal occupation of early Predynastic settlements in the First Cataract region – and beyond it as well – like their size or ephemeral architecture cannot be taken as a definite sign of temporariness. If, indeed, those communities chose to move seasonally, then the reason for such behavior was likely driven by other motivations. While data at hand do not completely support the assumption of early Predynastic communities being yearly settled along the Nile, that was clearly a possibility in most instances. The assumption that small settlements with ephemeral architecture equate to temporary sites must be reconsidered, particularly in a region such as the First Cataract, where there is no space for other types of settlements. The geo-archaeological data and the environmental potential for yearly use of water resources and, thus, for cultivation support the hypothesis that the settlement of Nag el-Qarmila and similar sites, at least in the area of the First Cataract, were used for the most part of the year, if not the whole year.

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Author Contributions

M.C.G. conceived and designed the analysis, collected and interpreted the geo-archaeological data, and wrote Sections 1, 2, and 3. O.S. designed the analysis, collected the archaeological and historic inundation data, performed the flooding modelling, and wrote Sections 4. Both authors wrote section 5.

Data Availability Statement

The datasets and shapefiles produced during and/or analyzed during the current study are available on Zenodo ([10.5281/zenodo.11619126](https://zenodo.org/records/11619126); <https://zenodo.org/records/11619126>).

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